

Report on Research Line 5

Inclusive Food Security and Sustainable Healthy Eating

Insights from ACCTING's Experimental Research

Research Cycle 2

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The ACCTING project

It is acknowledged by now that the global climate crisis is not only an ecological crisis but also an economic, social and political crisis, with devastating effects on individuals and societies. These negative effects are not evenly distributed within societies. It is the poorer, marginalised and vulnerable groups who are the most acutely affected, exacerbating existing socio-economic inequalities. The European Green Deal foresees efficient use of resources for a circular and clean economy. However, inequalities emerge in the context of its policy and interventions.

The EU-funded ACCTING project takes these considerations as a starting point for a complex series of research and experimental activities aimed at identifying, analysing and testing policies and initiatives capable of responding to this crisis, mitigating its effects on the most vulnerable and helping them play a significant role in the pursuit of greater environmental sustainability.

The project mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies and supporting behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

ACCTING explores the impact of Green Deal policy initiatives on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate policy responses and potential negative influences, and mitigate such impacts in decision-making. The project collects new data on Green Deal policy interventions and co-designs and implements pilot actions to reduce or prevent policy-related inequalities and advance behavioural change for an inclusive and equal European Green Deal.

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Disclaimer

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Introduction and methodology

This report presents a summary of findings from Research Line 5 of ACCTING's second cycle of experimental studies, which draws on data gathered from 87 quasi-experimental case studies conducted across thirteen countries between December 2023 and August 2024. Each research line explores sustainability and behavioural change within the framework of a specific European Green Deal policy area—including climate change, biodiversity, energy, food, and transport. This report focuses on food security and, more specifically, on the relationship between the participation of women and men in a local food system initiative and the changes in eating behaviour, analysing the conditions for this (individual, social and structural), from individual citizens and their families to collective actions at community level, in a perspective of sustainability.

All reports are available at <https://accting.eu/project-deliverables/>

1. Introduction

1.1 Sustainability, transformation and behavioural change in the context of RL5

With the rapidly growing urban population reaching 8,2 billion inhabitants in 2024 and the escalating climate crisis, the development of sustainable food systems has gained significant prominence in political debates worldwide. Key issues surrounding food security, such as the unequal distribution of food, and especially the need for access, in both physical and financial terms to nutritious, healthy and environmentally sustainable food are among the most pressing challenges faced by both the Global North and Global South (Viana et al., 2022).

Food has become a central focus of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the United Nations 2030 Agenda. It is also a cornerstone of the European Green Deal's ambitious goal of decarbonising by 2050, where the green economy – including food systems – plays a pivotal role in Europe's growth strategy. Transitioning towards sustainable food systems is critical for achieving the EU's climate neutrality objectives. That is why the Farm to Fork (F2F) strategy is a key element in transforming EU food systems, employing the One Health approach that integrates human, animal and environmental health. The aim is to make food systems more sustainable and resilient while ensuring a just transition, meaning that no one is left behind.

The ACCTING project specifically addresses the F2F strategy's core issues of food security, with a particular focus on food accessibility, healthy food consumption and waste mitigation. Europe's shift towards a sustainable food system will require profound transformations in how food is produced, processed, distributed and consumed (Fetting, 2020). This transformation necessitates behavioural changes at both individual and collective levels, supported by coherent policies at higher governance levels. However, behavioural change is complex and requires addressing motivation, ability and opportunity to adopt new practices. Furthermore, individual behaviour is shaped by broader societal barriers and levers, making change more challenging for some individuals and communities than others (Horst et al., 2024). This can lead to more socially unjust structures, disproportionately affecting vulnerable groups, including women (Abrantes et al., 2024; Béné et al., 2019).

Transformation and change must adopt a more human-centred approach, involving people in the decision-making process by utilising their knowledge and expertise (Reisch, 2021). People-centric frameworks, such as the FAO's Sustainable Food System Wheel and the socio-ecological model addressing behavioural change, are increasingly being integrated into food system approaches. These frameworks emphasise placing individuals and their resources at the centre of interactions with society and nature, recognising that human behaviour is complex, multidimensional, and influenced not only by individual characteristics but also by the contexts in which people live, from local to global levels (Abrantes et al., 2024).

Therefore, multiple layers of influence must be considered – from intrapersonal factors like attitudes and values, to interpersonal, organisational, community and policy (macro) levels, while a gender+ perspective in actions and policies is also crucial as gender roles and expectations can influence how different individuals and communities engage with food system sustainability (Abrantes et al., 2024; Grunert, 2014). In the first cycle of research in **Research Line 5 (RL5) – Food security and healthy diets** (exploratory), we provided an understanding of the key enablers and hindlers driving access (purchase and consumption) to healthy, affordable and sustainable food by individuals with different levels of vulnerability. For example, case studies from this first research cycle (RC1) of the project (Zorell & Strid, 2023) have shown that women have different consumption patterns and food-related behaviours compared to men, and they are affected by multiple hindering factors. In line with this framework, our research in the second research cycle (RC2) engages with multiple stakeholders, from individual citizens and their families to community-level collective actions, to track whether the participation in a local initiative (top-down or bottom-up) is relevant in changing women's and men's food behaviour (individual and collective, and not only participants in the initiative but also other stakeholders). Our goal is to learn from their practices, behaviours and actions concerning food security and healthy eating, and to co-produce new knowledge within this multilevel framework. This approach underscores the importance of addressing systemic inequalities and integrating people's lived experiences into the design and implementation of sustainable food systems.

1.2. Cases and contexts

In this second research cycle, each of the five partners selected two case studies, resulting in a total of ten cases. These cases were predominantly located in urban or in semi-urban / peri-urban contexts, except for the non-urban Austrian case of the "Garten der Begegnung". The cases span a range of initiatives, from community gardens focused on food production to social canteens and kitchens distributing food to vulnerable populations on the consumption side. The cases are described below.

Austria

Both cases are located in or near Vienna (one in Traiskirchen), Austria.

Case 1, Garten der Begegnung, is a community-based, donation-funded garden, established and managed by an NGO in Traiskirchen in Lower Austria. Traiskirchen is the first place where incoming refugees are registered and further assigned to other places in Austria to wait for their asylum decision. This refugee camp is active for more than 50 years. The garden is claimed to be the safest place in the municipality, being close to the police education and training centre. It is dedicated to fostering connections between refugees and locals through the shared experience of gardening. The garden initiative, established in 2016, centres around a 1-hectare garden where participants, mostly refugees, engage in ecological farming and many other activities. The garden is a vital space for growing vegetables, including traditional plants from refugees' homelands, unavailable in Austrian markets. The act of cultivation serves as both an integrating and empowering activity, allowing

refugees to reflect on their own cultural roots, learning gardening practice, also interacting with the local community.

Case 2, The Community Centre, is operated by the Vienna-based “Train of Hope” volunteer organisation, an NGO established in 2015 in response to the migration movements following the war in Syria. Since the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, the organisation has shifted its focus to supporting and partially integrating Ukrainian refugees in response to the ongoing crisis. Funded through donations and partially by the Vienna Social Fund, the Community Centre offers essential services like food, shelter and integration assistance. It provides daily hot meals as “excess food” from other social organisations such as the CARITAS. It also provides humanitarian aid and social activities. Moreover, it is serving as a crucial support hub, particularly for vulnerable groups such as women, children and elderly. Ukrainian refugees are also integrated as volunteers, leveraging their language skills to assist others.

Greece

Both cases are situated in the municipality of Thessaloniki.

Case 1, PERVOLARIDES, operates from its headquarters in the municipality of Pylaia-Chortiatis, while its cultivation field for vegetables and fruit is located in Liti, within the municipality of Oreokastro. Pervolarides is a project of social solidarity based on two pillars. The first one is the provision of immediate help to citizens in need. The second pillar is more future-oriented and deals with the circular and solidarity economy and the empowerment of citizens through joint actions and integration into the community.

Case 2, – Boroume, meaning “We Can”, is a non-profit organisation whose mission is to reduce food waste and to fight malnutrition in Greece. Boroume is active in many municipalities of Thessaloniki. However, the main area of focus is the municipality of Thessaloniki, which is the most central and multitudinous municipality of Thessaloniki regional unit. Through the “Saving & Offering Food” programme, the NGO saves food on a daily basis from many sources, and offers it to charities to help people who are facing food insecurity. The NGO’s actions help the most vulnerable in the society, as well as the environment by reducing organic food waste.

Portugal

Both case studies are located in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area, one in the municipality of Cascais and the other in the city of Lisbon.

Case 1, Terras de Cascais, is a project comprising several urban / community gardens in the municipality of Cascais, managed by the municipal company ‘Cascais Ambiente’, although the process originated in an associative experience. The majority of beneficiaries are low-income individuals, though only a few gardens have a significant concentration of vulnerable populations, one of which received special focus in the study.

Case 2, Alta de Lisboa Agricultural Park (PAAL), is located in the northern part of Lisbon, a newly urbanised area since the 1990s that includes rehoused populations from former shantytowns alongside middle-class residents. PAAL is the only urban garden in Lisbon managed privately by the Association for Environmental Enhancement of Alta de Lisboa (AVAAL), although it sits on public land. This initiative, which began as a citizen-led effort supported by the municipal authority, reflects the socio-economic duality of the neighbourhood, catering to both vulnerable and middle-class populations.

Sweden

Both cases are situated in the urban area of Stockholm.

Case 1, *Alla ska få mat (ASFM)*, is a bottom-up initiative started during the corona pandemic by one person and his friend to provide very poor and homeless people with free food. It receives food that would otherwise go to waste from wholesalers, and it raises money and collects other things for charity through a Facebook group. The organiser and varying volunteers cook at regular intervals in a restaurant that lets them use their premises in an industrial area in the northeast of the city. The core volunteers are mainly women and immigrants who are looking for opportunities to meet new people and get more integrated in the Swedish society through volunteering. The cooked, warm meals are delivered via volunteers to individuals and families in need all over the city. Furthermore, the cooking team brings food to homeless at the central station in the middle of the city. The meals are always vegan and cooked from rescued food, supplemented when needed by purchased ingredients. The main recipients of the food are, apart from homeless, single parents, disabled/sick individuals, families with many kids and little income, pensioners, and youths that do not get enough food at home.

Case 2, *Ny Gemenskap*, provides meeting points for people that are in economically and socially vulnerable situations. It has different branches in and outside of the city centre. The branch where fieldwork was conducted is in an industrial area in the southwest of the city. It is located somewhat away from where their target groups live, but it is easily reachable by bus. The place is a beautiful old Swedish house embedded in a small garden with a tiny forest around it. The branch has a nice seating area at the entrance where people can sit in the sun and eat/smoke. The initiative receives plenty of food that would otherwise go to waste every day from different supermarket chains, wholesalers and smaller sellers like bakeries. A small cooking team then prepares breakfast and lunch every day using all they have received, and the meals are sold at only a symbolic amount of money.

Turkey

Both cases are located within the Izmir Metropolitan Municipality.

Case 1, *Kadifekale*, is a community garden, first created in 2022 under "The Neighbourhood Gardens Project", which includes five gardens of varying sizes across five underprivileged areas, managed by the municipality. Positioned on the steep hills overlooking Izmir, Turkey's third-largest city with over 4.4 million residents as of 2022, this area has become an urban slum since 1950. Its character is shaped by a rich tapestry of cultural identities and diverse social and ethnic groups, largely stemming from internal migration from Kurdish-majority regions in southeastern Turkey due to conflicts in eastern and southeastern Anatolia. The neighbourhood has also welcomed Syrian refugees, who often communicate in Kurdish or Arabic and are under temporary or international protection, drawn by affordable housing, proximity to the city centre, job prospects, and an already established social network (Neslihan Demirtaş-Milz and Cenk Saraçoğlu, 2015). A community garden was established on previously neglected land in Kadifekale, which had remained vacant for years after houses were removed due to landslide risks. In its first year, 95 plots (each measuring 15-19 square meters) were utilised and 42 new plots were added in the second year due to significant demand. Since then, a total of 137 garden plots have been allocated each year, rent-free, to women residents of Kadifekale.

Case 2, *Mustafa Kemal, Buca*, is the second community garden set up by the Izmir Municipality as part of the Neighbourhood Garden Project. This neighbourhood also has a very high population density and limited green spaces. It stands apart from Kadifekale with its differences in demographic traits, operations and municipal services. This garden provides 30 women with garden plots, each measuring 15 to 19 square metres, free of charge for one year. Similar to the first garden, the municipality supplies seedlings, fertilisers, irrigation and farming tools, alongside with regular

agricultural training throughout the year. Women gardeners responsible for planting and crop production cultivate tomatoes, peppers, eggplants, okra, cucumbers and courgettes in summer, and they grow brussels sprouts, kale, broccoli, green beans and broad beans in winter.

Participant access

Accessing the necessary participants for interviews varied across cases, depending on the specific context and relevance to RL5. In Austria, Portugal and Turkey, it was relatively easier to identify and engage with vulnerable populations who participated as both producers and consumers in the food systems. However, in Austria, two-thirds of the citizens interviewed were solely consumers. In contrast, the recruitment process was more challenging in Greece and Sweden, and the participants accessed were exclusively consumers in Greece, and producers *or* consumers in Sweden (see detailed recruitment procedures below).

To provide a comparative overview of the key aspects of the different cases and initiatives, we present a synthesis of their main challenges and objectives (Table 1), as well as the vulnerable groups they targeted (Table 2). These tables organise and categorise the themes highlighted in the Country-Level Reports, enabling a structured comparison. The cases from the five countries reveal that several categories are reflected in each initiative, illustrating the complexity and multi-faceted nature of the interventions.

The first category groups topics focusing on social and community integration activities, as well as empowerment, usually involving gardens. The second category focuses on food production and healthy eating, through vegetable gardens. The third addresses food insecurity and waste reduction by providing meals and supporting vulnerable populations. The final category refers to the promotion of social cohesion and cultural integration, without necessarily implying vegetable gardens or food-related activities.

Table 1 – Challenges and aims of the initiatives

		Austria (AT)		Greece (GR)		Portugal (PT)		Sweden (SE)		Turkey (TR)	
Challenges and aims ↓	Initiatives / cases →	01	02	01	02	01	02	01	02	01	02
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration through gardening (AT, TR) • use of urban agriculture for social and community integration / environmental education and social integration practices (PT) • circular and solidarity economy and the empowerment of citizens through joint actions and through integration into a community of people (GR, SE) • Women (community) empowerment (TR) 	X		X		X	X	X		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of vegetables (AT) • promotion of organic urban agriculture and healthy eating (PT, SE) • increasing access to healthy, safe, nutritious and seasonal food + promoting ecological urban agriculture and healthy eating for food-insecure populations (TR) 	X				X	X	X			X	X
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Address food insecurity by provision of meals / cooking opportunity + Opening up to local inhabitants (AT) • reduction of food waste and food insecurity + provision of immediate help to citizens in need (GR) • provide cheap / free, healthy, plant-based meals to homeless/people in need; use only rescued food / reducing food waste (SE) • Poverty alleviation (TR) 	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X

		Austria (AT)		Greece (GR)		Portugal (PT)		Sweden (SE)		Turkey (TR)	
Challenges and aims ↓	Initiatives / cases →	01	02	01	02	01	02	01	02	01	02
		• Enhance community support and cohesion + Facilitate cultural integration (AT, SE) • to be a venue for companionship for the lonely (SE)			X					X	

In the second table below, the first category groups topics focusing on the various types of vulnerable population, while the second category is more specific, limited to groups of citizens in diverse situations, where vulnerability is relative.

Table 2 – Addressed vulnerable groups of the initiatives

		Austria (AT)		Greece (GR)		Portugal (PT)		Sweden (SE)		Turkey (TR)	
Addressed vulnerable groups ↓	Initiatives / cases →	01	02	01	02	01	02	01	02	01	02
		• Refugees, migrants and asylum seekers (AT,SE,TR) • women/gender specific situation + children (caretaking) + people facing language barriers (AT) • people with low SES, migrants, elderly (GR,PT) • people with disabilities or special health related needs / sick individuals (AT,GR,PT,SE,TR) • Homeless (GR,SE) • low income families, single parents (GR,SE,TR) • families with many kids (SE,TR), pensioners, youth, drug addicts, unemployed / in employment programmes, Roma (SE) • women and children with multiple vulnerabilities + children in the neighbourhood (TR)		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
• Local people with no garden (vulnerability limited) (AT) • in need of a vegetable garden: relocated people coming from slums, but not only, involving limited vulnerability (PT) • state primary schoolchildren: a class in the neighbourhood elementary school has their own space in the garden (TR)		X				X	X			X	

2. Methodology and study materials

The study takes a quasi-experimental approach, following real-life initiatives in conducting activities that aim to improve food security, healthy eating and ecological food consumption. The research was conducted in ten case studies within five countries. On the one hand, the intervention logic was aimed to let verify to what degree factors identified in RC1 enable and/or hinder behavioural changes in terms of access to food, healthy diets and combating food waste. On the other hand, we observed that the setup permitted us to examine what role different initiatives or activities play in the processes inherent to these changes. In this quasi-experimental framework, we generated data using qualitative methods and resources. First, indirect data collection through desk research was crucial in framing the chosen initiatives. This approach provided essential context and helped guide the process of obtaining primary data. It also enabled a deeper understanding of the broader environments in which the initiatives operate. In this case, the individuals targeted for the study – whether they were involved as both producers and consumers, or solely as consumers – represented two distinct situations that were examined across the different organisations and initiatives.

Secondly, primary data collection was predominantly conducted through semi-structured interviews, which accounted for nearly 75% of all interviews. These interviews involved 57 citizens (primarily vulnerable individuals) and key members from 16 initiatives (stakeholders and collective entities). In addition, unstructured interviews were used in 9 cases (Portugal and Sweden) and focus group interviews were conducted in another 9 cases (in Greece, Sweden and Turkey). Whenever possible,

interviews were recorded with informed consent. In certain cases, however, recording was either not feasible or the recordings were not usable, due to factors such as participant refusal, technical difficulties, or challenges in understanding individuals with limited language proficiency. Nevertheless, detailed written notes were taken to ensure that all necessary information was captured for the interview reporting templates; consent was obtained in all instances.

The interview questionnaires – comprising both closed and open-ended questions – were primarily designed for individuals involved in food production, but also included numerous questions for those who were ‘solely consumers’. Participant observation was incorporated in a flexible and adaptive manner across the different case studies, allowing for the collection of additional insights, which were then transferred to the interview reporting templates as complementary information and clarification.

The entire set of information was synthesised by each research team, resulting in country-level reports. These reports were essential for providing an integrated, comprehensive and complementary analysis of the primary data, along with insights drawn from the interview reports.

3. Collected data and analysis

3.1. Recruitment procedures

In the various case studies, similar procedures were followed to gain initial access to the key individuals relevant to the objectives of RL5, as well as to ensure their availability. Initial contacts, dating back to 2023, were made with members of the organisations and influential figures or persons with responsibilities in the gardens. In some cases, this included access to horticultural production sites linked to the initiatives, particularly involving vulnerable populations.

However, the procedures differed slightly depending on the specific approaches taken by each research team, which were influenced by the nature of the organisations and the conditions or preferences for accessing the target individuals.

From the cases investigated by ZSI (Austria), AT01 significantly used the garden producer and sole employee of the initiative as a mediator for the recruitment, putting the research team and both women and men in contact within a group of volunteers active in horticultural activities. In the other case (AT02), the selection was supported by the active leading team of the initiative and personal contacts and inquiries of the interviewer. Then, the leader contacted the contributing volunteers and interviews were arranged according to availability.

The Greek research team contacted key people working in both initiatives (non-profit organisations) to introduce the researchers and explain who they are, the project they are undertaking, and the overall aims of both the project and the research line. They were very positive about the aim of the project and showed genuine interest in helping. With their assistance, two focus groups were organised (one for each case study). In the first case (Boroume) three participants attended. The first focus group was successful, with all three participants actively participating in conversational manner. In the second focus group, six participants attended some of whom were more reserved, while others took most of the focus of the conversation. Efforts were made to encourage wider participation, but the preference of some to remain reserved was respected.

The Portuguese research team resorted to the support of people who gave rise to the targeted initiatives. One of them, a former leader, provided the most relevant contacts for the interviews, including the current leader of the initiative (AVAAL / PAAL). Both were interviewed in 2023 and provided answers to follow-up questions in 2024 to meet the interview objectives. Recruitment of

participants from the PAAL garden was facilitated by these initial connections, as well as through insights gained from participant observation during various visits to the garden, which helped capture the specific contexts of each moment.

In the second case, the research team leveraged previous contacts with staff members to select the most relevant urban gardens for the study, ultimately conducting interviews in two gardens, with a primary focus on one. In May 2024, the team interviewed the founder of what is now called 'Terras de Cascais,' part of the municipal company 'Cascais Ambiente' (CA). This person, who also holds a senior position within Cascais Ambiente, provided insights into the origins and overall state of the urban gardens, particularly regarding the challenges faced by a diverse range of users, especially vulnerable populations. A challenge faced during fieldwork was reaching women, because they generally work more than men in the region (in vulnerable groups and in general), primarily outside the gardens. As a result, only about one-third of the beneficiaries interviewed are women. Despite this, the researchers were able to gather valuable explanatory information about the absent women through other interviews, including with stakeholders, such as garden managers, and a female leader from a local association with an immigrant background.

The Swedish team initially planned to conduct a study with Matmissionen, Sweden's largest food bank. However, after a stakeholder interview in November 2023, it became evident that proceeding in 2024 was unfeasible. The harsh winter in turn meant urban gardens were closed. Subsequently, the relevant case of ASFM was found, enabling a connection with the first stakeholder interviewed from Ny Gemenskap, the second case study. Both organisations seemed to be an ideal fit because they are bottom-up organisations driven and largely sustained by highly engaged volunteers. They receive rescued food from wholesalers and food stores, thus contributing to reducing food waste and improving access to healthy and environmentally sustainable food for the most marginalised individuals in the city, including homeless and those socially sidelined by age, health issues, income, family size, ethnic origin and/or language. At ASFM, the researcher joined cooking and distributing the food. However, interviewing recipients of the food turned out to be very difficult. Only short conversations were possible, or people refused to give an interview. At Ny Gemenskap, only one person was willing to be interviewed. The others asked were unfamiliar with research and lacked trust, finding themselves in a tense environment in which they need to be careful; e.g., on a day of field work, there was a knife attack on the Ny Gemenskap manager by a guest (knives were mentioned as a big problem by different local persons). Yet, various interviews could be conducted with helpers in the initiatives.

The Turkish team discovered both cases through a planting video shared on the municipality's social media. In 2023, they conducted several formal and informal visits during the planting seasons. They established connections with two key local municipal teams: the Emergency Solution Team, formed in 2019, and Mercek (meaning 'Lens' in English). These local government teams focus on empowering vulnerable individuals and communities in low-income or underserved neighbourhoods that lack adequate public services and resources, promoting greater citizen engagement. When the SU researchers held targeted focus group interviews with these teams in 2024, they gained important insights and information about the stories behind each garden and the women who utilised them. The Mercek team, a distinctive initiative started in 2021 within the Youth Studies and Social Projects Department of the Izmir Municipality, was crucial in selecting interviewees due to their direct interactions with the women garden users. Their assistance was essential for facilitating a smooth process in both gardens. Recruitment in case 2, Mustafa Kemal, another low-income neighbourhood in Izmir, posed more significant challenges than Kadifekale, as this community garden lacked seating and a pergola for shade and in May, when the interviews were conducted, it was very hot thus making

interviews more difficult. Unlike Kadifekale, no municipal staff were stationed in the garden due to insufficient office space. Since women were accustomed to socialising outside the garden because they lacked a physical space, they usually arrived, worked in the garden, and then left. However, waiting for their turn would have been cumbersome, therefore the research team decided to schedule the interviews after the communal planting session, thus making it easier for them to reach the women. Needing an indoor, shaded location for the interviews, the researchers utilised the cafeteria of the local sports club adjacent to the garden area. Although the space was predominantly used by men, the owner, who also manages the local football club, ensured it remained quiet for the interviews.

3.2. Sample description and vulnerability factors

Data collection for RL5 involved 73 interviews conducted in urban, semi-urban and peri-urban environments, though some interviews included multiple participants, such as members of organisations or initiatives (notably in Sweden and Turkey). As a result, the total number of participants reached 78, with 31% from Austria, 13% from Greece, 24% from Portugal, 10% from Sweden, and 22% from Turkey. These participants contributed in varying ways to the overall data collected.

As shown in Table 3, women constituted a larger proportion of participants in Austria and Turkey, while there was gender balance in Greece and Sweden. Portugal, however, showed a clear gender imbalance, primarily due to the lower availability of women in the gardens, as many were occupied with other jobs or responsibilities, reflecting ‘gendered pressures’. Younger participants were most prominent in Turkey and Austria, followed by Sweden and Greece, while Portugal had the largest representation of older participants.

Table 3 – Main features of primary data collection from interviews – semi-structured (SSI), unstructured (UI), and through Focus Groups (FG) –, both to Citizens (Ctz) and stakeholders / leading members of initiatives (Stk¹)

Country	Case Studies (location)	Nr. of Interviews	Geographic context	Gender of Ctz & Stk people	Ages
Austria	Traiskirchen; Vienna	19 SSI (Ctz) 5 SSI (Stk)	9 in a town or small city 10 in a big city	15 women + 4 men (Ctz) 5 women (Stk)	[16 ; 73] (Avg 50)
Greece	Thessaloniki	8 in FG (Ctz) 2 SSI (Stk)	All in a big city	4 women + 4 men (Ctz) 1 woman + 1 man (Stk)	[29 ; 73] (Avg 56)
Portugal	Cascais; Lisbon	10 SSI + 5 UI (Ctz) 2 SSI + 2 UI (Stk)	8 in suburbs or outskirts 7 in a big city	5 women + 10 men (Ctz) 1 woman + 3 men (Stk)	[34 ; 85] (Avg 66)
Sweden	Stockholm	1 UI (Ctz) 2 SSI + 1 UI + 1 in FG (Stk)	In a big city	1 man (Ctz) 4 women + 3 men (Stk)	[30 ; 67] (Avg 42)
Turkey	Kadifekale, Izmir; Buca, Izmir	14 SSI (Ctz) 1 SSI (Stk)	All in suburbs or outskirts of a big city	14 women (Ctz) 2 women + 1 man (Stk)	[29 ; 54] (Avg 41)

For the purposes of the following analysis, we have designated “vulnerability factors” both the disadvantageous directly collected during the interviews (e.g. a certain migratory background, low levels of education or income), as well as the conditions signalled by the researchers according to a previously defined list for general comparison, in this case with the specific designation of Subjective Inequalities (SI).

In terms of vulnerability factors, the elements outlined in tables 4 and 5 highlight some comparative aspects. On the one hand, subjective inequalities (SI) are primarily influenced by nationality or migrant status in the cases of Austria and Turkey, with language and gender also playing significant roles. In contrast, social class/socio-economic background are more prominent factors in Greece and

¹ Detailing the interviewee(s) and type of initiative of “Stk”: Austria – 3 women from association A and 2 women from association B; Greece – 1 woman from an association and 1 man from a network; Portugal – 1 man from a local authority, 1 woman from association A, 2 men from association B; Sweden – 1 man and 4 women from a network and 2 men from association B; Turkey – 1 man and 2 women from a local authority.

Portugal, though they are also important in Austria. Although gender is not the most dominant factor among SIs, it ranks among the top four key factors overall.

When comparing the relative proportion of subjective inequalities (RWSI) between women (W) and men (M), in three of the countries studied², the share of SI is significantly higher among women in Portugal (W=4.4; M=2.2) and Austria (W=4.0; M=3.2) than in Greece, where the amount is equal for both genders (2.3).

Age, particularly advanced age, is a notable vulnerability factor in the sample of Portugal, where it intersects with ethnic, racial or socio-economic backgrounds, as well as in Greece. Additionally, in Portugal, there is a high presence of disabled individuals.

Table 4 – Comparative data on the origins, education and income levels of the interviewed citizens

Country	Nat. background Born / not Born	not Born => Where from?	Migration background	Education	Income
Austria	0 / 19	Ukraine (9), Syria (5), Venezuela (2), South Africa, Nigeria & Palestina (1 each)	None of the two (5), mother + mother and father (2), Not asked/no answer (12)	No degree (3), Sec. School (6), Univ. Degree (9), Prof. training degree (1)	Finding it difficult on present income (7), Finding it very difficult on present income (12)
Greece	8 / 0		None of the two (8)	Element. School (2), Sec. School (6)	Finding it difficult on present income (8)
Portugal	8 / 7	Cape Vert (5), Angola & Guinea-Bissau (1 each)	None of the two (11), Not asked / no answer (4)	No degree (3), Element. School (10), Sec. School (1), Univ. Degree (1)	Finding it difficult on present income (5), Finding it very difficult on present income (1), Coping on present income (5), Living comfortably on present income (4)
Sweden	1 / 0		Mother (1)	Elementary School	Living comfortably on present income
Turkey	11 / 3	Syria (5), Eastern Turkey (1)	Yes, mother and father (9), None of the two (5)	No degree (6), Element. School (4), Sec. School (3), Prof. training degree (1)	Finding it difficult on present income (8), Finding it very difficult on present income (2), Coping on present income (4)

Table 5 – Subjective inequalities among the interviewed citizens: frequency of records and main highlights by country

Subjective Inequalities (SI)	Austria	Greece	Portugal	Sweden	Turkey
SI1 Not applicable	0		0		0
SI2 No subjective inequality	0		3		1
SI3 Gender	8	4	5		3
SI4 LGBTQ+ status	0	0	0		0
SI5 Age	5	4	8		0
SI6 Disability	2	1	6	1	1
SI7 Nationality and/or migrant status	19	0	5		6
SI8 Religion/belief	0	0	0		0
SI9 Language	18	0	1		3
SI10 Ethnic, racial, and/or social origin	5	0	7		2
SI11 Social class/socioeconomic background	15	8	8	1	1
SI12 Geographic location	1		0		0
SI13 Other	0		1		0
SI14 Prefer not to say					

The first, second and third highest values in each country are highlighted.

The overall assessment of income and education indicators, along with the non-national origins of several interviewees (Table 4) completes the vulnerability factors (VF) previously mentioned. In Austria, Turkey, and Portugal, most individuals with lower education levels reported finding it difficult or very difficult to manage on their current income. An exception is in Austria the presence of Ukrainian refugees, many of whom have university degrees but also are in difficult economic situations. However, approximately 30% of respondents in Portugal and Turkey indicated that they are coping with their current income (able to manage reasonably), and in Portugal, four individuals even reported living comfortably. These cases are often characterised by a mix of health-related vulnerability factors and “no subjective inequality,” with respondents being neighbours of community garden users who

² For the three countries in which there are women and men as citizens interviewed (in Turkey there are only women), the relative weight of subjective inequalities (RWSI) was obtained with the following index: $RWSI(G) = (Total\ SI / Total\ G)$, where G is the number of men or women.

possess valuable insights into local sustainability practices and conditions, offering a comparative perspective on other opinions. In contrast, the respondent from Sweden reported living comfortably on the present income, yet it is unclear to what extent this is an accurate assessment or result of the interviewee not willing to admit the dire circumstances in which he seemed to live as described in the rest of the interview³.

Although vulnerability factors and subjective inequalities were systematically identified only for the citizens interviewed, most of the members interviewed from the two Swedish organisations also had backgrounds marked by some form of vulnerability – unlike most of the cases in the other countries. In fact, among the seven individuals interviewed across four interview sessions in Sweden, only one did not have an immigrant background: five were originally from Brazil (arriving at different times), and one from India (though raised in Sweden from a young age). Interestingly, these subjective inequalities became assets within the organisations, as these individuals brought about valuable skills in cooking and/or prior experience in volunteering, contributing to the outcomes discussed below.

Despite the various types of vulnerability encountered in all cases, several members of vulnerable groups actively participate in different roles within the initiatives, as outlined in the overview provided in Table 6.

Table 6 – Active Participation and Roles of Vulnerable Groups within Initiatives

Role of vulnerable groups ↓	Initiatives / cases →	Austria (AT)		Greece (GR)		Portugal (PT)		Sweden (SE)		Turkey (TR)	
		01	02	01	02	01	02	01	02	01	02
	• A supervising gardener + Women’s day, peer to peer exchange + cooking session participation / social events (AT) • participating in the cultivation of the garden (GR)	X		X							
	• Active volunteers in food /meal distribution + cultural exchange facilitators in community events (AT) • delivering food to those who cannot + companionship, moral and social support (SE) • Knowledge sharing / mutual help between neighbours / users in the garden or other people in need (PT,GR, TR) • sharing experience, resources including the food they grow + creating solidarity in and out of the garden providing + translation between different languages (TR)		X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X

3.3. Analysis

3.3.1. Behavioural change and impact within and across countries

3.3.1.1. An overview of changes in food security and their contexts

Looking at participants in the initiatives who were interviewed (not the members of the initiatives), we begin by distinguishing between citizens who were only consumers (C) and those who were both producers and consumers (P&C), as shown in Table 7. This separation is important because the types of changes experienced, as well as the resulting impacts, vary significantly depending on the individuals’ relationships with the initiatives or organisations. The most pronounced differences with

³ Indeed, even other self-assessments of greater or lesser comfort with income can be biased by personal and cultural characteristics and can have different meanings in different contexts. Let’s say, greater or lesser demands regarding material conditions (there may even be full satisfaction with access to basic needs), together with the perception of relative fairness, may influence the perception of income adequacy. We therefore have some reservations about the significance of this variable, which should be considered in combination with others.

the greatest implications are found in Turkey, particularly in the Kadifekale (Izmir) case. There, the majority of participants reported that access to food was located far from their homes or workplaces.

In the cases where participants were only consumers, such as in Austria (where this is predominant), Greece, and Sweden (where this is the sole category), participation in the initiatives positively impacted everyone by improving access to food and/or by providing valuable information about food and nutrition: Austria's case 1 has positively impacted access to both fresh produce and information or improved knowledge about nutritious food and healthy eating. For example, the interviewee Naza, from Syria, notes, "[i]n Austria I eat many vegetables, many fruits", reflecting the dietary changes she embraced. The interviewee Maryna mentions "[t]his is a very good savings on such money". She also highlights her experience with food preparation and the introduction to different nutritional habits, saying, "I realised that beet leaves... are very useful". Other citizens emphasised the regular access to meals and fresh produce – or “regular meals and social support” – and “access to balanced meals”. Greece's Pervolarides case has mostly impacted the perspective of food waste practices, improving access to information and knowledge on quality and nutritional value of food, and on agricultural production processes. In the focus group, participants revealed that they were shocked on the amount of food that is thrown away in farmers' markets, when they collaborated on an event about reducing food waste organised by the initiative. Some interviewees revealed also improvement in their food security, including a weekly provision “with a fresh bag of goods”, and learning much, especially about different fertilisers and chemicals used in conventional farming, and about exact timelines of production and seasonality of different fruits and vegetables.

In the other cases, the P&C category, participation in the initiatives also had a positive impact in general. There is only one exception among the respondents from Austria and another from Portugal (i.e., no differences were recognised between before and after participation).

Table 7 – Physical access to food and perceptions of the interviewees* of the initiative's influence on changing food-related behaviours and practices – absolute and comparative data regarding the profiles 'Both Producer and Consumer' (P&C) and Just 'Consumer' (C)

TOTALS (100%) of C and P&C	Austria		Greece	Portugal	Sweden	Turkey
	C (13)	P&C (6)	C (8)	P&C (15)	C (1)	P&C (14)
Most of the food is got...						
In a place distant from home or workplace				1 (7%)		8 (57%)
Near both home and workplace				2 (13%)		1 (7%)
Near home	13 (100%)	6 (100%)	8 (100%)	12 (80%)	1 (100%)	5 (36%)
Participation in the initiative made a difference... (Yes)	13 (100%)	5 (83%)	8 (100%)	14 (93%)	1 (100%)	14 (100%)
Practices have changed...						
food consumption	13 (100%)	1 (17%)	2 (25%)	3 (20%)	1 (100%)	1 (7%)
food waste practices		5 (83%)	6 (75%)	1 (7%)		
purchasing habits				2 (13%)		1 (7%)
other				7 (47%)		12 (86%)
Experience in the garden...						
changed previous knowledge	5 (38%)	6 (100%)	5 (63%)	12 (80%)		12 (86%)
changed the way of cooking	5 (38%)	3 (50%)	6 (75%)			
changed the food eaten at home	2 (15%)	3 (50%)	6 (75%)	12 (80%)		13 (93%)
contributed to improving the degree of healthy eating	5 (38%)	6 (100%)	6 (75%)	14 (93%)	1 (100%)	13 (93%)
The initiative contributed to improving...						
food security	3 (23%)		6 (75%)	11 (73%)	1 (100%)	13 (93%)
social links	5 (38%)	6 (100%)	5 (63%)	12 (80%)	1 (100%)	14 (100%)
food literacy	2 (15%)	4 (67%)	7 (88%)	10 (67%)	1 (100%)	13 (93%)

Stakeholders / leading members of the initiatives not included

The interviews with some consumers (C) revealed positive reflections on their experiences with the garden(s), even though they were not involved as producers or P&Cs. This positive influence can be attributed, in part, to the proximity of the garden and the indirect benefits of the initiatives, particularly

in the case of Pervolarides, though notable instances were also reported in Vienna. Additionally, participants mentioned past experiences (more so than current ones) that had some degree of influence. These factors, overall, contributed to enhanced knowledge about food, improvements in cooking practices, changes in food choices, and an increased consumption of healthy foods. In the case of Pervolarides, the initiative's contributions to food security and food literacy were particularly significant (75% and 88% of respondents, respectively). The results of the interviews of P&Cs include answers to the same indicators as consumers, as well as additional ones, shown also in Table 7. With regard to 'Practices have changed...' (the question 'How have food purchasing, consumption and waste practices changed since the launch of the initiative?'), we can highlight one particularity in the responses from Portugal and Turkey: they cover all the options in the question, and seem to give little weight to each of the first three. However, this is due to the fact that the 'Other' option generally concerns (around 80%) a combination of two or three of the previous options. The contents of the 17 responses from Austria, Portugal and Turkey are shown here, being merely illustrative of the diversity of the initiatives' outcomes (Table 8).

Table 8 – Open response elements of 'How have food purchasing, consumption, and waste practices changed since the initiative's launch?' (equal contents: numbers in round brackets)

"We make compost", referring to her using food scraps for composting, a practice she learned through the initiative	[RL5_RC2_C1_AT07]
Both purchasing habits and food consumption changed (3)	[RL5_RC2_C1_PT06 + PT03+PT06]
Buying fewer fresh vegetables, and choosing better them (being more selective about quality)	[RL5_RC2_C1_PT03]
Combination of purchasing habits, food consumption and food waste practices (2)	[RL5_RC2_C2_PT02+PT04]
Composting is an interesting practice that he has not seen before, this is a learning outcome of the garden and the related social interaction with the gardening team	[RL5_RC2_C1_AT02]
Healthier food purchasing habits	[RL5_RC2_C1_AT05]
Helping a friend was the change (2)	[RL5_RC2_C1_PT05+PT06]
More careful about buying seasonal food after she started coming to the garden	[RL5_RC2_C1_TR03]
New practices of recycling	[RL5_RC2_C1_PT01]
The initiative has significantly improved her food purchasing habits and reduced waste by providing fresh, organic produce and teaching sustainable practices, including composting.	[RL5_RC2_C1_AT01]

Considering what factors seem to enable change in food security, individual resources (Figure 1), namely knowledge and education, are particularly important in Austria, followed by perceived self-efficacy and access to social and political actors. In Turkey (as in Greece), access to both equipment and social and political actors is the primary enabler, with knowledge also playing a significant role. In Portugal, the availability of time stands out in particular – largely due to the weight of the age in the sample and the proximity of vegetable gardens to residences –, followed by knowledge.

When examining micro-level factors that hinder change in food security (as also outlined in Figure 1), financial constraints are evident in almost all cases. In Portugal, education stands out as a hindering factor, referring to the low levels of formal qualifications. However, this is partly offset by informal knowledge gained through past experiences in small-scale farming. Despite this, informal knowledge

can also make individuals more vulnerable, particularly older people and those with an immigrant background. This is especially true for employed women, who often face challenges in adapting to new learning and knowledge updates due to their occupations or other responsibilities.

Figure 1 – Individual resources in change: Enabling and hindering factors at the micro-level – insights from citizen interviews

Similarly, in the insights from interviews with members of the initiatives (Table 9), especially time emerges as a significant barrier in the Portuguese cases (from the perspective of organisation members). Financial constraints are also mentioned as the primary hindrance in these cases, but even more so in cases from Austria. Several resources, however, including the conditions and dynamics of each initiative (collective behaviours), contribute positively across different cases and support various types of change, as captured in the following extracts from the interviews:

A. Changes in terms of food and eating conditions

Donations and volunteers' engagement (time, equipment, food, skills, food literacy) are mentioned as enablers (C2_RL5_SE01_CSO_1).

Knowing how to find and prepare healthy organic food, along with knowledge on the nutritional value of different foods, emerges as a strong factor facilitating change towards more environmentally sustainable habits and practices (C2_RL5_GR01_P).

Having knowledge of what actually food waste is and how it affects both society and the environment seems to be an important enabler for changing behaviour. Also, the knowledge of food-saving techniques seems to be important. In addition, being self-aware of the quantities of food someone needs, while also limiting the waste that he/she produces is a very important factor for feeling self-efficient and eventually changing behaviours (C2_RL5_GR02_P).

One interviewee noted, "we Africans (...) we cook a lot" and "there is an awareness of what waste is: I waste very little at home, because it is effectively a resource; rice is expensive, pasta is expensive, so we always try to eat everything and reuse it as much as possible until we finish (...). This mindset is common in most households, though perhaps less so than before." (C2_RL5_PT01_CSO_1).

Factors impacting healthy food access include time constraints and economic limitations. AVAAL and PAAL aim to increase healthy food options in the "Alta de Lisboa" neighbourhood. Yet, time availability has posed a challenge for both the interviewee who manages complex responsibilities within AVAAL, and vulnerable residents engaged in working to improve the access to healthy food. Economic limitations further restrict participation, except for those with higher incomes. The interviewee's education and social networks facilitated change, though these resources are less accessible to more vulnerable groups (C2_RL5_PT02_CSO_2).

B. Changes regarding the conditions of the initiative and involvement in it

The interviewee's background in engineering and previous work experiences have equipped her with valuable skills and knowledge, enabling her to adapt and contribute effectively to the initiative. "I am from Western Ukraine, I am 37 years old. I studied engineering for automatic control and regulation of computers at the university." Education has been a significant enabler, providing the skills necessary for various roles. "So, I asked to join the laboratory where my husband worked, if there were any vacancies, to work there as well." The ability to communicate in German and take initiative has helped the interviewee secure her current role. "And our colleague, who now works in the kitchen, Peter, I approached and tried to explain in German that I needed something to eat." Access to necessary equipment in the workplace has facilitated her duties (C2_RL5_AT02_CSO_2).

Factors indicate a shift toward broader structural and societal change. Designed to foster qualified and inclusive urban regeneration, AVAAL and PAAL (Portugal) initially depended heavily on the mentor's initiative, availability of personal time, education, and connections to launch and manage these projects. Access to political and social networks further supported that transition to an essay of structural and societal change (C2_RL5_PT02_CSO_1).

Given the variety of activities and the available support, the durable experimentation with new ways of acting has enabled a complex and sustainable way of organising the integration garden in Austria (case 1). The experiences and partnerships with several actors in the municipality (including the municipal administrations but also the social sector, refugee camps and CARITAS) have activated necessary knowledge and created positive synergies. Thanks to the only employee being a gardener, continuous presence of gardening knowledge is secured. Educational tasks are embedded in the gardening practice, occasionally paired with information provision during work done in the garden. Most important is the outreach to schools that visit the garden and get insights while also contributing with work force. Self-efficacy and own experience, but also the confidence the surrounding stakeholders is clearly an enabler for the activities (C2_RL5_AT01_CSO_1). The community garden in Traiskirchen thrives due to several enabling factors, including strong political support, diverse volunteer knowledge, and access to equipment through federal grants. The mayor's backing has provided municipal land and occasional funding, facilitating diverse programmes like gardening and sports. Volunteers' expertise in education and IT support enriches the initiative, while flexible time management allows for an effective participation (C2_RL5_AT01_CSO_2).

The Garden of Encounters initiative benefits significantly from various resources that enable its success. Volunteers, particularly retirees, dedicate substantial time, enriching the project with their expertise and commitment. Informal German lessons and agricultural training sessions improve participants' skills and confidence. The availability of necessary

gardening tools facilitates efficient work. The interviewee Lara noted, "We have practically no machines. That means things happen by squatting, with back work, with arm work". Strong connections with local authorities, schools, and associations bolster the initiative by providing additional resources and collaborative opportunities. Lara explained, "There are workshops. For example, people from companies come for a morning to garden here. There are schools that come regularly". These resources collectively enable the project to achieve its goals of fostering community engagement, ecological sustainability, and social integration (C2_RL5_AT01_CSO_3).

The initiative has benefited greatly from the time and dedication of volunteers. The interviewee Lisa mentioned, "In the association, I have to count eight in total, eight. Of which two are cleaning staff and four are caregivers. But these are all part-time positions (...)". Knowledge and experience brought by individuals who have worked in similar projects have been vital. As Lisa said, "I have a mixed background; I have cultural experience in the educational field, in management, and in communications. That's perfect." Education and training have empowered volunteers and staff to effectively support refugees. Access to equipment and tools has been facilitated through donations from local businesses, which have provided essential resources like food and hygiene products. Lisa highlighted, "We get a maximum of 500 portions daily from the city, but we have up to 2,000 people arriving. (...) And we looked for cooperation partners, found several food producers who supported us with food donations over a shorter or longer period" (C2_RL5_AT02_CSO_1).

Table 9 – Enabling and hindering factors of change - Individual resources (micro-level factors after interviews to stakeholder / leading initiative members)

Individual Resources	Enabling Factors of Change ¹					Hindering Factors of Change ¹				
	Austria	Greece	Portugal	Sweden	Turkey	Austria	Greece	Portugal	Sweden	Turkey
Time	4	0	2	2	0	1	0	3	1	1
Money	1	0	2	1	0	4	0	3	1	1
Knowledge	5	1	2	1	1	0	0	2	0	0
Education	4	1	3	1	1	1	0	2	0	0
Perceived self-efficacy	4	1	3	1	1	1	0	2	0	0
Access to equipment	5	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	1	0
Access to political and social actors	3	0	3	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
Other	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

¹ No. of answers.

In terms of social dynamics, the factors that enable change are dominant, compared to the hindering factors, both among citizens (Figure 2) and among the members of the initiatives interviewed (Table 10). Being part of the community or a social network is the main factor in all countries, followed by having meaningful relationships. For the Austrian cases, feelings of social appreciation also stand out.

Figure 2 – Social dynamics in change: Enablers and barriers at the meso-level – insights from citizen interview

Drawing on the contributions of the initiative members interviewed (Table 9), the various cases reveal a broad pattern consistent with citizen-related results across different types of change:

A. Changes in terms of food and eating conditions

From the interviewees’ perspectives, positive interactions within garden spaces have encouraged healthier food access for vulnerable populations, partly due to a diverse mix of backgrounds. However, certain beliefs and cultural values, particularly among individuals of African origin, can sometimes hinder the adoption of more efficient production and consumption methods (C2_RL5_PT01_P_1).

Reducing waste to a minimum within vulnerable communities, hinges on fostering community belonging and forming meaningful relationships in and beyond garden spaces. Intergenerational exchanges between elders and younger generations, who often receive environmental education, can reinforce values supporting sustainability (C2_RL5_PT01_CSO_1).

The participation in the initiative is seen as a privilege with a wider societal outreach, embedding social goals, educational goals. Food production in the garden gives access to food not available elsewhere. Circularity is an output that refers to the practices that organic production brings with a new understanding to the contributing volunteers. With regards to the wider outreach to society, the embeddedness of the present organisation in the municipality is key. Social appreciation is practiced e.g in the cooking sessions, in the oriental brunches each Saturday that gives positive feedback to the contributors, gardeners (C2_RL5_AT01_CSO_1).

The social dynamics within the initiative primarily act as enablers. Being part of a community network and having significant relationships have shown to foster trust and support, essential for the success of the programme. Joint activities, such as gardening and the Saturday Oriental Breakfast, create a sense of belonging and mutual appreciation among participants. This is especially crucial in a city like Traiskirchen, which hosts a large refugee centre, as it helps bridge the gap between locals and newcomers, promoting social cohesion. On the other hand, certain beliefs and values can sometimes hinder participation: cultural and religious differences may pose challenges, necessitating a careful and inclusive approach to activity planning (C2_RL5_AT01_CSO_2).

B. Changes regarding the conditions of the initiative and involvement in it

Much of the activities seem to build on personal connections and networks, both when it comes to recruiting volunteers, as well as when it comes to reaching out to the people in need. Also, the feeling of being able to help others who are less well off and contributing actively to the local community has been mentioned as driver of volunteers, while those receiving food feel appreciated and more socially included (C2_RL5_SE01_CSO_1).

Intrinsic motivation seems to be key as well to do this job. It has become a semi-safe environment in the past years, with people carrying knives, stealing, sometimes being very demanding and rude. But individual values and conviction seem to be relevant factors motivating to do this work (C2_RL5_SE02_CSO_1).

According to Maria, the sense of belonging, both for the volunteers and the beneficiaries, and the empowerment of the latter is an enabling factor. Maria also mentioned that the formation of real and deep relationships between volunteers and people in need is very important for sharing common values and moving forward together (C2_RL5_GR01_P).

Alex mentioned that for many vulnerable people, being part of a larger community (when for example they go to take part in an action of a specific NGO) empowers them and makes them more receptive to changing their habits, as they can share their thoughts, exchange ideas and change their way of thinking (C2_RL5_GR02_P).

The social dynamics favoured particularly the mentor of the initiative for its success, as he was part of advantageous communities of practice (university, in particular) and had favourable relationships involving leadership and trust, as well as feelings of social appreciation, with the contribution of own beliefs and values in the field of civic ecology (C2_RL5_PT02_CSO_1).

The social dynamics benefited the interviewee, contributing to both his personal success and the success of the initiative. As an active member of the community, he developed a deep understanding of local cultures and cultivated favourable relationships, beginning during his university years and extending into his work in community organizations. This environment fostered leadership, trust and social appreciation, underpinned by Catholic-inspired values of solidarity. These factors enabled the mentor's initial efforts to drive meaningful changes, promoting access to healthier food and lifestyles aligned with the initiative's goals. However, among the most vulnerable populations, these supportive conditions are often lacking, presenting challenges to achieving similar outcomes (C2_RL5_PT02_CSO_2).

Social networks and community involvement have been crucial enablers, fostering a sense of belonging and mutual support among refugees and volunteers. Lisa mentioned, "We then made sure to divide the entire initial care into different areas. So, we have the area of volunteer coordination." Significant relationships built on trust, care and leadership have strengthened the initiative's impact. The initiative has managed to create an environment where social appreciation is a strong motivator, encouraging continuous volunteer engagement and community participation. Lisa noted, "We sometimes specifically said we need people who speak the language. And that's how it developed. Oh, incredible." Collaboration among volunteers has been a key factor in the initiative's success. (C2_RL5_AT02_CSO_1).

The support and inclusion in the Ukrainian community in Austria have been beneficial. "And there, in Austria, we have a centre, called the Stadium for some reason, it's called Stadium.", mentioned Diana. Relationships with colleagues and leadership have provided substantial support and encouragement. The sense of being valued and appreciated in her role has a positive contribution. "Plus, I can help. What is very important and pleasant for

me, why I love my job, is constant communication". On the other hand, negative perceptions and lack of appreciation among some community members can be demotivating. Diana shared: "Although people I know, I worked with people and work now less than before." (C2_RL5_AT02_CSO_2).

Table 10 – Social dynamics in change: Enablers and barriers at the meso-level – insights from stakeholder / initiative member interviews

Social Dynamics	Enabling Factors of Change ¹					Hindering Factors of Change ¹				
	Austria	Greece	Portugal	Sweden	Turkey	Austria	Greece	Portugal	Sweden	Turkey
Being part community or S.N.	5	2	4	1	1	0	0	0	0	1
Having significant relationships	5	1	4	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
Having certain beliefs and values	2	0	3	1	1	3	0	2	0	0
Feelings of social appreciation	5	0	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Other	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

¹ No of answers

With regard to structural conditions, mentions of hindering factors of change sometimes outweigh enabling factors, both among citizens (Figure 3) and initiative members (Table 11). Notably, in the cases of Greece and Sweden, members mention exclusively hindering factors. Physical geography, environment conditions, as well as infrastructure, are the most significant negative influences, particularly in Turkey, and to a lesser extent, in Portugal.

Figure 3 – Structural conditions in change: Macro-level enablers and barriers – insights from citizen interviews

Interviews with the initiative members / leaders provide valuable insights into these situations, highlighting variations in the relative impact of specific factors (Table 11):

A. Changes in terms of food and eating conditions

One season, The Mercek Team faced a water shortage in the garden, resulting in inadequate produce for the women, particularly water-intensive vegetables like aubergine, which required lots of water due to insufficient irrigation. To compensate for this, women were allowed to cultivate their gardens for an additional period (C2_RL5_TR01_P).

Lack of interest and support by public authorities and politics is mentioned as major hinder for the initiative to operate at the level that would be required to truly have an impact on improving food access, security and healthy eating of the vulnerable groups which they want to support (C2_RL5_SE01_CSO_1).

Local policies of the municipality like closing the public taps or cutting down trees, while at the same time not getting involved in issues like food waste are reasons that hinder change in both personal and collective levels (C2_RL5_GR01_P).

The lack of engagement of public authorities in the issue of food waste in the city is a major hindering factor for change, as the community bypasses the issue which does not gain the visibility and importance it needs (C2_RL5_GR02_P).

Although favourable edaphoclimatic conditions and infrastructure (e.g., equipment and water access) exist, political and policy support from the Municipal Authority's food strategy is limited by economic and social challenges. These constraints inhibit individual resources like time, money and knowledge. Economic hardships push residents to save resources and reduce waste, but often at the expense of their quality of life (C2_RL5_PT01_P_1).

Physical geography (sloping, rocky terrain in the PAAL area) and inadequate infrastructure (lack of equipment, limited water access) hinder change. However, politics and policies and the demand for critical, inclusive innovations serve as enablers in response to the crisis (2008–2012). Additionally, projects like K'Citade, driven by the Aga Khan Foundation and partners, have positively influenced the area (C2_RL5_PT02_CSO_1).

Economic constraints and national political climates can sometimes hinder the initiative, limiting resources and creating challenges for refugee integration. Cultural differences and language barriers also pose occasional difficulties. Despite these challenges, the initiative significantly impacts by providing access to healthy, environmentally friendly food and promoting waste reduction. More importantly, it fosters social inclusion and aims for broader societal change, integrating refugees into the community and reducing xenophobia. These efforts collectively contribute to the initiative's sustainability and its positive influence on the community (C2_RL5_AT01_CSO_2).

B. Changes regarding the conditions of the initiative and involvement in it

The expensive public transport combined with the venue being somewhat outside in an industrial area make it difficult for some people to access the place. More people are coming in summer than in winter, probably also because of the location. International conflicts and rising poverty in turn make it more difficult to achieve their goals since every more individuals are becoming "vulnerable" (C2_RL5_SE02_CSO_1).

In spite of the availability of the garden area, being a key structural condition as a big enabling factor, together with the infrastructure, self-empowerment is a difficult endeavour for the refugee/asylum camp where people stay only for short time periods. The rule to transfer people to other countries camps changes the situation for persons that do not see a true sense to become engaged given the challenge of an unplannable perspective, where nobody can be sure where he or she will be next week (C2_RL5_AT01_CSO_1).

Social and economic conditions have presented mixed effects; while local donations and volunteerism have been positive, the overall economic strain has limited the extent of support. Lisa explained, "We had this confirmed before we signed the lease. A month later, it was no longer remembered, and the costs were not fully covered, only 75%". Policies and

politics have often hindered the initiative, with bureaucratic challenges and insufficient funding posing significant obstacles. Lisa noted, "The city promised to provide food for the people in the arrival centre. They did not do that from the first week onward." (C2_RL5_AT02_CS0_1).

Table 11 – Structural conditions influencing change: Macro-level enablers and barriers – insights from stakeholder / leading initiative member interviews

Structural Conditions	Enabling Factors of Change ¹					Hindering Factors of Change ¹				
	Austria	Greece	Portugal	Sweden	Turkey	Austria	Greece	Portugal	Sweden	Turkey
Physical geography & environment	4	0	1	0	1	0	0	2	1	0
Infrastructure	5	0	2	0	0	1	0	2	2	1
Social and economic conditions	3	0	1	0	0	3	0	2	0	0
Policies and politics	3	0	4	0	1	2	2	0	1	0
Events and developments	5	0	2	0	1	2	0	0	1	0
Other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

¹ No of answers

Regarding the key question of what changes have occurred in the community since the initiative's inception, interviews with initiative members and leaders yielded the following findings (Table 12), based on responses to closed-ended sub-questions (Yes, No, and Don't Know/Not Applicable):

Table 12 – Community changes since initiative launch: Insights from stakeholder / leading initiative members

What Has Changed in the community since the start?	Austria	Greece	Portugal	Sweden	Turkey
Increased production of fresh, locally sourced food	Yes = 4; *... = 1	No = 2	*... = 1; Yes = 3		Yes
Greater environmental care in local food production	Yes = 4; *... = 1	Yes = 2	*... = 1; Yes = 3		Yes
Increased consumption of fresh, locally sourced foods	Yes = 5	No = 1; Yes = 1	*... = 1; Yes = 3		Yes
Greater care / greater demand when choosing purchased foods	No = 1; Yes = 4	No = 1; Yes = 1	*... = 4		Yes
Greater care in food preparation	Yes = 5	Yes = 1; No = 1	*... = 4		Yes
Improving practices for using food, against waste	Yes = 5	Yes = 2	*... = 4		Yes
Improving the nutritional quality of diets	No = 1; Yes = 4	*... = 1; Yes = 1	*... = 2; Yes = 2		Yes
Improving social inclusion and reducing inequalities	Yes = 5	Yes = 2	Yes = 4		Yes
Improving solidarity across social groups and classes	Yes = 5	Yes = 2	Yes = 4		Yes
Greater participation of women in the process of improving Food Security	Yes = 5	No = 2	Yes = 2; *... = 2		Yes
Is the initiative creating added value... ?	Yes = 5	No = 2	No = 1; Yes = 3	No = 2; Yes = 2	Yes
Is collaboration / partnerships changing?	Yes = 5	No = 2	Yes = 4	Yes = 4	Yes
Is the initiative promoting & achieving active community engagement / commitments?	Yes = 5	Yes = 2	Yes = 4	Yes = 4	Yes

*... Don't know / don't apply

Table 12 provides a summary of the overwhelmingly positive perspectives shared by initiative members on community changes observed since each initiative's launch. These changes encompass improvements in the production, acquisition and consumption of locally sourced fresh food, along with efforts to reduce waste, enhance the nutritional quality of diets and promote environmental stewardship. Additionally, members noted increased social solidarity, inclusion and participation – particularly among women. Exceptions largely pertain to areas beyond the organizations' direct influence.

To address potential differences in how questions in Table 12 were interpreted, a complementary clarification has been included, drawing from interviewer notes to aid in understanding and explaining the nature of behavioural changes observed. This adapted text (in Tables 13 A, B, C, D, E) is condensed for clarity while aiming to maintain accuracy and representation of the original responses.

The interviewer notes did not always provide sufficient information to classify observations under the four types of change considered – namely, added value, changes in collaboration/partnerships, changes in active community engagement, and other changes. This was particularly the case for the interviews conducted in Greece and Sweden, which explains the missing columns in Tables 13B and 13D.

Tables 13 A, B, C, D, E – Insights on the initiative's added Value, evolving collaboration, community engagement, and other changes: perspectives from stakeholders' interviewees

Table 13 A – Overview of Changes in the Austrian Cases

Added value	Changes in collaboration / partnerships	Changes in active community engagement	Other changes
<p>1. Openness to new ways of organising the gardening; open access recreational part in around half of the entire place as a low intensity agricultural area (ecological compensation, maintained by bringing for some days a goat's herd)</p> <p>2. Market opportunities for local producers by selling organic produce, supporting local entrepreneurship and promoting the consumption of healthy, locally-grown food; open-access recreation zone available to all local community members</p> <p>3. Fostering entrepreneurship and market opportunities for local producers through its community market and workshops.</p> <p>4. Market opportunities through the increased demand for locally sourced food boosting both the local economy and the entrepreneurship (by encouraging small-scale food production and distribution); fostering a sense of community and mutual support, enhancing the overall well-being of community members</p> <p>5. Opportunities for volunteers to gain practical experience and for community members to engage in meaningful activities; a platform for social interaction and support, enhancing the overall well-being of the community</p>	<p>1. Depends on volunteering / motivated persons, the main resource; schools too, as workshops are organised (involving gardening, some pedagogic activities)</p> <p>2. Involving the municipality and other NGOs, facilitating resource sharing and enhancing the initiative's impact</p> <p>3. Collaborations have strengthened, leading to more integrated and supportive community networks</p> <p>4. Collaboration between various actors has significantly increased, with the initiative fostering partnerships with local food producers, catering companies, and other organizations, helping to leverage surplus food and resources, ensuring a steady supply of nutritious meals for refugees</p>	<p>1. Children summer activities of the municipality are hosted in the garden, but also companies come to work on team building activities; two companies send their employees to support the initiative.</p> <p>2. Gardening together with the local population and people with migration experience has a strong community aspect that is particularly important for cities like Traiskirchen, with a huge refugee centre</p> <p>3. Through regular workshops, events, and inclusive activities that encourage community participation</p> <p>4. Community engagement by involving volunteers in various activities, such as food distribution, cooking, and organising events at the community centre</p> <p>5. Active community engagement by involving community members in various activities, such as volunteering, attending courses, and participating in social events. The initiative's structure encourages people to take part in the organization and running of its programmes, fostering a sense of ownership and commitment</p>	<p>1. Empowerment activity including women and a community building action to enable solidarity: community of practice for "starting to cook" and "starting to gardening", "becoming self-organised" and enjoying still the guidance of the qualified gardener on site</p> <p>2. Promotion of healthy living, education, and inclusion through a collective and professional approach; teaching of children about food sources (healthy agriculture) and sustainability; involvement of more migrants and refugees in decision-making</p> <p>3. Increased fresh, locally sourced food production, with greater environmental care (e.g. reducing food waste) and healthier dietary habits (nutritional quality of diets), after improving the efficiency of food usage; fostering of social inclusion, reducing inequalities and increasing the participation of women in the process</p> <p>5. More healthier food options, new to many community members; improving solidarity and a sense of community and support among participants, enhancing social inclusion, actively involving women.</p>

Table 13 B – Overview of changes in the Greek cases

Changes in active community engagement	Other changes
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<p>1. More than a main occupation, directly related to food (securing and sorting food), other social issues of the community are also dealt with (e.g., claim the reopening of public taps in the city, so that every citizen could have access to clean drinking water without having to buy it from a store; participation in movements against the cutting of trees in the city)</p> <p>2. Through its educational programmes, and especially their presentations in schools, Boroume engages actively with the community by cultivating the values of sustainability and solidarity</p>	<p>1. Greater support to the life cycle of locally produced food; good practices learned and passed on in the community; daily operation of social inclusion and empowerment</p> <p>2. Vulnerable groups have now a dignified access to fresh, locally produced vegetables and fruit; both volunteers and beneficiaries now have a better understanding of nutritional quality of diets, food waste, and the importance of purchasing only the necessary quantities when shopping.</p>
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Table 13 C – Overview of changes in the Portuguese cases

Added value	Changes in collaboration / partnerships	Changes in active community engagement	Other changes
<p>1. Multiplication of community gardens, in different neighbourhoods, creating more opportunities for people with different types and degrees of vulnerability</p> <p>2. Mostly informal added value may be recognised for vulnerable citizens, as some use garden produces collected from several of the plots that do not belong to them (stealing) to sell in small 'markets of opportunity' (according to different local interviewees, which do not know or cannot reveal who the people involved in this)</p>	<p>1. Depends on the projects and new needs, but includes a) associations / charities of social action receiving vegetables from the garden inside the prison of Tires; b) local schools, receiving support for their Vegetable Gardens (e.g. environmental education, technical support and training, production factors)</p> <p>2.. Some have occurred within the scope of new projects (funded and/or supported somehow by the Lisbon Municipality and some important NGO)</p>	<p>1. Through both the information and opportunities provided by the own means, in addition to the conversations/interactions in dissemination sessions, workshops, etc.</p> <p>2. To the extent of the activities that are necessary, often with stimuli from the Municipality / Cascais Ambiente, and usually related to the work with children and young people, also very focused on the issues of vegetable gardens</p> <p>3 + 4. Particularly at an early stage, and later through occasional collaborations in the field of volunteering that AVAAL and nearby organizations promote.</p>	<p>1. Greater incorporation into the diet of local fresh vegetables (consumption on the day or later, due to the use of refrigerators and freezers); greater participation of women in the process of improving food security</p> <p>2. Greater importance of the collaborations inherent to the conviviality developed, but also some loss of interest in the training of 'Cascais Ambiente' (from older or busier people)</p>

Table 13 D – Overview of changes in the Swedish cases

Added value	Changes in collaboration / partnerships	Changes in active community engagement
<p>1. Information and informal education for visitors about food, healthy eating and environmental issues (e.g. eating vegetarian, the value of rescued food vs. food waste; food literacy (e.g. best before dates and learning to listen to own sense before throwing out food)</p> <p>2. Enabling food companies the possibility to reduce their food waste; contribution to reducing social isolation and loneliness, as well as hygiene and thus health</p>	<p>1. Positively, the coordination of the volunteers, food receivers, and food donators seems to work pretty smoothly; however, access to financing and collaboration with local authorities seems to be difficult because Stockholm municipality has stopped its financial support</p> <p>2. It is expanding to more and more actors</p>	<p>1. Many volunteers help regularly, both at cooking and at distributing the food. The food donations come in weekly as well.</p> <p>2. Volunteers are helping every day, some of them also offering courses (e.g., music, arts)</p>

Table 13 E – Overview of changes in the Turkish cases

Added value	Changes in collaboration / partnerships	Changes in active community engagement	Other changes
<p>1. Newly launched project, 'Seeds of Empowerment,' in collaboration with the IOM (twenty migrant women from the garden growing cacti in a greenhouse set up near the garden, promising future income for their families by selling these cacti).</p>	<p>1. Many offices that the Team collaborated with within the scope of the neighbourhood garden project have undergone radical changes. Some have closed. Even the office to which the Team is affiliated has changed (e.g. the project has been affiliated with the women's studies unit).</p>	<p>1. Despite women gardeners are mandated to visit the garden at least twice a week, many of them choose to spend more time than required: they come every day after sending their children to school. They actively participate in the workshops, engage in social interactions, and share their everyday life experiences, fostering a strong sense of community.</p>	<p>1. Consume vegetables more in the household while paying more attention to buying seasonal and pesticide-free food in the bazaar.</p>

The types of behavioural changes observed in the community since each initiative's inception are closely tied to the surrounding circumstances. In other words, the core characteristics of the organization and the processes it develops shape the nature of collective changes – such as the emergence of new collaborations or partnerships – and also influence individual changes within the community.

Collective changes, particularly in collaborations and partnerships, are essential drivers of transformation, enabling new forms of co-responsibility and resource complementarity in addressing societal needs and challenges. In Turkey, Portugal and Austria, a significant portion of collaborative efforts centres around vegetable gardens, which notably impacts women and children through various associated activities. Beyond these three countries, cases in Greece and Sweden also include initiatives that enhance vulnerable groups' access to healthy food, contributing to similar positive outcomes.

Across all five countries, these changes encompass various forms and dimensions of education – particularly social and community education, which is often informal – as well as training, or more accurately, learning contexts that support and accompany change. Schools play a central role in several cases: in Sweden, for instance, volunteer work complements learning, while in Austria, volunteering is also a key component. Schools are involved through student and teacher visits to gardens for environmental education (Austria and Portugal), as venues for project presentations promoting sustainability and solidarity values (Greece), as supporters of school-based gardens (Portugal), and as institutions enabling women to engage more fully in garden activities while their children participate in school programmes (Turkey).

In the interplay between collective and individual behavioural changes, women play a prominent role, especially in Austria and Turkey, where aspects of empowerment are significant. In Greece, empowerment is also linked to the inclusion of people in disadvantaged situations. The emphasis on healthy eating and nutrition is particularly strong in Sweden and Austria, and to a lesser extent in Portugal. Additionally, in these countries – as well as in one Greek case – initiatives incorporate efforts to combat food waste, which represents important aspects of the observed changes.

3.3.1.2. A specific focus on food security factors

Using selected indicators from those already included in Table 7, with the purpose of complementing the analysis done in 3.3.1.1, we start by addressing the most general indicator: 'The initiative contributed to improving food security' (Table 14).

Table 14 – Level of connection between the enabling and hindering factors of behavioural change and the variable “The initiative contributed to improving food security” for the participants

Individual Resources	Enabling Factors of Change					Hindering Factors of Change				
	Austria	Greece	Portugal	Sweden	Turkey	Austria	Greece	Portugal	Sweden	Turkey
Time	0,0	0,3	1,0	1,0	0,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,1
Money	0,0	0,0	0,4	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,5	0,6	0,0	0,2
Knowledge	0,7	0,5	0,6	0,0	0,7	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,1
Education	1,0	0,2	0,1	0,0	0,2	0,0	0,0	0,4	0,0	0,0
Perceived self-efficacy	0,7	0,2	0,4	0,0	0,1	0,0	0,0	0,1	0,0	0,0
Access to equipment	0,0	0,0	0,1	0,0	1,0	0,0	0,2	0,1	0,0	0,0
Access to political and social actors	0,0	0,0	0,2	0,0	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,2	0,0	0,0
Other	0,3	0,0	0,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,1	0,0	0,0
Social Dynamics										
Being part community or social network	1,0	0,0	0,9	1,0	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Having significant relationships	1,0	0,8	0,5	1,0	0,9	0,0	0,0	0,1	0,0	0,0
Having certain beliefs and values	0,0	0,3	0,1	0,0	0,2	0,0	0,0	0,1	0,0	0,0
Feelings of social appreciation	1,0	0,0	0,5	1,0	0,4	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,2
Structural Conditions										
Physical geography & environment	0,0	0,0	0,3	0,0	0,6	0,0	0,5	0,5	0,0	1,0
Infrastructure	0,0	0,0	0,3	0,0	0,6	0,0	0,0	0,5	0,0	1,0
Social and economic conditions	0,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,6	0,7	0,8	0,3	0,0	0,5
Policies and politics	0,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	0,7	0,2	0,2	1,0	0,0
Events and developments	0,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	0,0	0,1	1,0	0,0

Table values between 0 and 1 – ratio between the number of ‘Yes’ answers (associations between the variable and each factor) of each country and the expected theoretical maximum (number of possible answers, matching each factor and each variable).

Confirming the ideas obtained from the analysis carried out earlier in a more general way, the most relevant factors that facilitate the initiative's contribution to improving food security are the following: a) in terms of individual resources, ‘knowledge’ and, secondarily, ‘education’ and ‘perceived self-efficacy’; b) in terms of social dynamics, ‘having relevant relationships’ is highlighted, but ‘being part of a community or social network’ and ‘feelings of social appreciation’ are also important, except in the case of Greece.

Of the factors that hinder the initiative's contribution to improving food security, although ‘money’ appears with some prominence among the countries of the South, the ones that stand out are mainly in the area of structural conditions. We are referring to ‘economic and social conditions’, which are complemented by ‘physical geography and the environment’ (in the southern countries) and ‘politics and policies’, in this case with the notable exception of Turkey, where this factor is a facilitator (distinctive role of local government).

In order to facilitate a contextualised clarification of these realities – what the links between the above-mentioned factors of the initiative's contribution to improving food security mean – we have added other related variables to this variable. These new variables reflect the initiative's contribution to changes in food literacy, consumption behaviour and diets, and the role of garden experiences in these changes. To do this, we used the same type of analysis (of connectivity between factors and variables), but selected only the factors we had highlighted, within each level, from micro to macro (Tables 15, 16 and 17).

Table 15 – Key variables analysed on food access and consumption that best connect with the factors of behavioural change – Individual Resources / micro-level factors (level of connections*)

Enabling and hindering factors of change	Main Variables	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Knowledge as enabler	Austria	0,9	0,8	0,7	0,5	0,7	0,8	0,7	0,8
	Greece	0,5	0,6	0,5	0,7	0,6	0,5	0,5	0,7
	Portugal	0,7	0,9	0,6	0,7	0,8	0,6	0,6	0,3
	Sweden							0,0	
	Turkey	1,0	0,7	0,7	1,0	0,8	0,8	0,7	1,0
Education as enabler	Austria	0,6	0,3	1,0	0,3	0,5	0,2	0,5	0,4
	Greece	0,0	0,1	0,2	0,3	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,3
	Portugal	0,0	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,0
	Sweden								
	Turkey	0,0	0,2	0,2	1,0	0,3	0,3	0,2	0,0
Perceived self-efficacy as enabler	Austria	0,6	0,3	0,7	0,3	0,4	0,6	0,4	0,4
	Greece	0,0	0,1	0,2	0,0	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,0
	Portugal	0,7	0,6	0,4	0,4	0,6	0,4	0,4	0,0
	Sweden								
	Turkey	0,0	0,1	0,1	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,1	0,0

Key variables

A. Food consumption has changed since the start of the Initiative

B. The initiative contributed to improving food literacy

C. The initiative contributed to improving food security

D. How the initiative has contributed to improving food security (elab.)

E. Experience in the garden has changed previous knowledge

F. Experience in the garden has changed the food eaten at home

G. The garden contributed to improving the level of healthy eating

H. How the garden has contributed to improving the level of healthy eating (elab.)

Spaces represented on a green background: matching factors and variables when we have in at least four of the five countries

* Table values between 0 and 1 – ratio between the number of ‘Yes’ answers (associations between the variable and each factor) of each country and the expected theoretical maximum (number of possible answers, matching each factor and each variable).

Considering micro-level factors, knowledge seems to be significantly involved as an enabler of behavioural change in the initiative's contribution to food literacy, food consumption and food security in general, as well as in the contribution of experiences in the gardens to changing prior knowledge about food and diet quality. Education also follows roughly the same pattern, although with less presence in the variables ‘food consumption has changed’ and ‘How has the garden contributed to improving the level of healthy eating’, in this case based on open-ended answers. Perceived self-efficacy only seems to be relevant as an enabler of behavioural change in the contribution to food literacy and food security in general, and in the contribution to improving healthy eating. As illustrative references from the interviews, we have:

Anna is a Nigerian refugee living in Vienna for nine years. Anna's farming experience in Nigeria provided her with valuable agricultural skills, which have benefited her gardening activities in Vienna (...). Her familiarity with consistent weather patterns and plant cultivation has helped her adapt to gardening in a new climate (RL5_RC2_C1_AT05)

Anele learned about new vegetables and gardening techniques. She mentioned planting tomatoes and other plants, which expanded her knowledge of fresh produce and gardening. Although not formally educated in Austria, Anele attended German courses and participated in gardening activities, indirectly gaining education about local agricultural practices and the nutritional benefits of different foods (RL5_RC2_C1_AT06)

Awira gained new cooking skills and knowledge about different cuisines, such as learning to cook Afghan dishes from other women in the community. Participating in courses offered by Caritas and the garden project (...) has provided Awira with new skills and education. This has indirectly impacted her ability to engage with new foods and recipes, promoting healthier and more diverse food consumption (RL5_RC2_C1_AT08)

Through the project, Naza has learned about healthier eating habits, including the consumption of more vegetables and fruits, and reducing the intake of meat and butter.

Participating in gardening and cooking activities at the project has boosted Naza’s confidence in her ability to grow and prepare healthier foods, influencing her dietary choices positively (RL5_RC2_C1_AT11)

Maryna’s knowledge and previous experiences, particularly her pedagogical background and involvement in nutrition-related projects, have been significant enablers in her ability to adapt and contribute to the initiative. Her education has provided her with skills and the ability to handle information effectively. Perceived self-efficacy has empowered her to take an active role in the initiative, despite challenges (RL5_RC2_C2_AT01)

This man has (...) comprehensive general knowledge, although without relevant formal education bases, due to having life experience and easy relationships with different people as sources of learnings; perceived self-efficacy is also an advantage, enabling him to humorously induce behavioural changes among the nearby school population (RL5_RC2_C2_PT01)

This woman has (...) general knowledge about practical horticulture, as she has life experience when using the backyard in the past, and also follows medical guidelines, which favours healthier eating options (RL5_RC2_C2_PT08)

She has some knowledge about planting and growing food and hoeing. This is certainly an enabler. As she sadly mentioned, she was not sent to school at her rural village because, as a child, she went to planting with her family in the village (RL5_RC2_C2_TR06)

With regard to the meso-level factors relating to social dynamics, all four considered show some relevant expression (Table 16).

Table 16 – Key variables analysed on food access and consumption that best connect with the factors of behavioural change – Social Dynamics / meso-level factors (level of connections*)

Enabling and hindering factors of change	Main Variables	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Being part of the community or Social Network as enabler	Austria	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0
	Greece	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	Portugal	1,0	0,8	0,9	1,0	0,8	0,9	0,9	1,0
	Sweden	1,0		1,0				1,0	
	Turkey	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0
Having significant relationships as enabler	Austria	0,9	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0
	Greece	0,0	0,7	0,8	0,7	1,0	0,8	0,8	0,7
	Portugal	0,3	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,6	0,4	0,4	0,3
	Sweden	1,0		1,0				1,0	
	Turkey	1,0	0,9	0,9	1,0	0,9	0,9	0,9	1,0
Having certain beliefs and values as enabler	Austria	0,1	0,3	0,0	0,8	0,5	0,4	0,5	0,6
	Greece	0,0	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,4	0,3	0,3	0,3
	Portugal	0,3	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,0
	Sweden								
	Turkey	0,0	0,2	0,2	0,0	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,0
Feelings of social appreciation as enabler	Austria	0,8	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0
	Greece	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
	Portugal	0,7	0,6	0,5	0,5	0,6	0,5	0,6	0,0
	Sweden	1,0		1,0				1,0	
	Turkey	1,0	0,4	0,4	1,0	0,4	0,5	0,4	0,0

Key variables

A. Food consumption has changed since the start of the Initiative

B. The initiative contributed to improving the food literacy

C. The initiative contributed to improving the food security

D. How the initiative has contributed to improving the food security (elab.)

E. Experience in the garden has changed previous knowledge

F. Experience in the garden has changed the food eaten at home

G. The garden contributed to improving the level of healthy eating

H. How the garden has contributed to improving the level of healthy eating (elab.)

Spaces represented on a green background: matching factors and variables when we have in at least four of the five countries

* Table values between 0 and 1 – ratio between the number of ‘Yes’ answers (associations between the variable and each factor) of each country and the expected theoretical maximum (number of possible answers, matching each factor and each variable).

Having significant relationships is the only enabling factor of change for all the selected key variables, but the other factors listed (being part of the community or social network, having certain beliefs and

values, and feelings of social appreciation) also reveal significant expressions as enablers in the correspondence with three or four variables. Given the importance of these meso level factors, some illustrative references reported from the interviews include:

It's not only the food security aspect but also being among her fellow Ukrainians that is important (RL5_RC2_C2_AT03)

The speaker's joy in sharing her harvest with her neighbours is palpable. She recalls with pride the time when her neighbour gave her some of the eggplants she grew in the garden, and she didn't have to buy any eggplants even when she didn't have a garden in the project. This experience of sharing and receiving from the community is what she aims to replicate in the first harvest, as she plans to distribute the eggplants to her neighbours. It seems like it is not just about the produce, but about the connections and relationships that are nurtured through the act of gardening (RL5_RC2_C2_TR06)

She stressed the importance of the community effect in the garden initiative, as she refers to it: "We cook together, we eat together, we play together, we work together in the garden" (RL5_RC2_C1_AT05)

Her involvement in cooking activities also played a significant role; she learned new recipes and cooking techniques from other women, which she enjoyed sharing with her family (RL5_RC2_C1_AT08)

The support and encouragement she receives, along with opportunities to contribute (e.g., through gardening and cooking), enhance her sense of belonging and self-worth (RL5_RC2_C1_AT11)

Enable behavioural changes in everything related to food production refer to having significant relationships, in particular concerning the garden (RL5_RC2_C2_PT07)

Behavioural changes in everything related to food (production and consumption) refer to being part of the community and having significant relationships, especially in the garden (RL5_RC2_C1_PT03)

She said the food she grows in the garden tastes similar to that in her hometown since they don't use chemical fertilizers or pesticides in the community garden. She believes that the food in her village was/is "natural". However, it is well known that villagers or farmers in the villages use various chemicals while growing food and lack the traditional knowledge for adopting (pesticide-free) ecological practices for protecting natural spaces and growing food (RL5_RC2_C1_TR04)

With regard to the macro-level factors / structural conditions with relevant expression, only three were selected, all of them being hindering factors of behavioural change (Table 17).

Table 17 – Key variables analysed on food access and consumption that best connect with the factors of behavioural change – Structural Conditions / macro-level factors (level of connections*)

Enabling and hindering factors of change	Main Variables	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
Physical geography & environment as hinder	Austria	0,1	0,2	0,0	0,3	0,1	0,0	0,1	0,1
	Greece	0,5	0,6	0,5	0,0	0,6	0,5	0,5	0,0
	Portugal	0,7	0,4	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,4	0,4	0,0
	Sweden								
	Turkey	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0	1,0
Social and economic conditions as hinder	Austria	0,5	0,5	0,7	0,5	0,5	0,4	0,5	0,5
	Greece	1,0	0,7	0,8	0,7	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,7
	Portugal	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,3	0,2	0,0
	Sweden								
	Turkey	1,0	0,5	0,5	0,0	0,4	0,4	0,5	0,0
Policies and politics as hinder	Austria	0,3	0,0	0,7	0,0	0,2	0,0	0,2	0,0
	Greece	0,5	0,1	0,2	0,3	0,0	0,2	0,2	0,3
	Portugal	0,3	0,2	0,2	0,3	0,3	0,2	0,2	0,0
	Sweden			1,0				1,0	
	Turkey	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0

Key variables

A. Food consumption has changed since the start of the Initiative

B. The initiative contributed to improving food literacy

C. The initiative contributed to improving food security

D. How the initiative has contributed to improving food security (elab.)

E. Experience in the garden has changed previous knowledge

F. Experience in the garden has changed the food eaten at home

G. The garden contributed to improving the level of healthy eating

H. How the garden has contributed to improving the level of healthy eating (elab.)

Spaces represented on a green background: matching factors and variables when we have in at least four of the five countries

* Table values between 0 and 1 – ratio between the number of ‘Yes’ answers (associations between the variable and each factor) of each country and the expected theoretical maximum (number of possible answers, matching each factor and each variable).

Of these factors, ‘social and economic conditions’ stand out, showing the greatest importance in six of the eight key variables. This is followed by ‘physical geography and the environment’ for four of the variables, and ‘policies and politics’ for three of them. As an example of illustrative references reported in the interviews, we have, only for people who are only consumers, not both producers and consumers (P&C):

Catalina highlights the significant change in her social and economic status. In Venezuela, she worked as an accountant, but now she lives in a refugee centre in Austria. Being placed in a primary reception centre shows how national and European policies affect her living conditions and access to resources. She mentions that in Venezuela her brother has a large farm with diverse crops like manioc, oranges, and bananas, which contrasts with the types of plants she encounters in Austria, and the difference highlights how physical geography and environment can impact her adaptation process [RL5_RC2_C1_AT09]

Daniela's experience highlights the significant impact of social and economic conditions on her life in the refugee centre. The lack of facilities to cook their own meals reflects the broader economic constraints and social structures within the centre. As shared: "Then you can't cook. And that's really important for the women". This refer to the refugee centre's regulations and policies, dictating that meals are prepared for residents and not allowing personal cooking: "because in the centre everything is prepared" (RL5_RC2_C1_AT10)

In Syria, she had access to a large garden, whereas in Vienna, she lacks personal gardening space, affecting her ability to grow her own food. The "Garten der Begegnung" project helps mitigate this by providing shared gardening spaces, enabling her to continue this practice. The economic disparity between her life in Syria and Austria is evident. While she ran small businesses in Syria, she now relies on community support and social services (RL5_RC2_C1_AT11)

George talked a lot about the role of political and economic interest behind the food chain in Greece, and globally. He mentioned that in the name of money, everyone is pushed to buy from big supermarket chains and to only purchase global brands and labelled products (RL5_RC2_C1_GR03).

Thanos mentioned increased prices that make it difficult to access food and also maintain a vegetable garden or a green house, but he also mentioned that society has changed, and most people prefer the ready-to-consume food and don't take the time to cultivate their own even if they could afford to. He also mentioned that city life makes it much harder to cultivate products so one is reliant on supermarkets to access food which lacks quality (RL5_RC2_C1_GR05).

The physical geography and environment, including the infrastructure challenges of relocating to a new country, have posed difficulties. Adjusting to the different living conditions and navigating the urban landscape of Vienna has been a significant hurdle (RL5_RC2_C2_AT01)

The social and economic policies in Austria provided Petro with essential resources (...), but they are still not enough to maintain the life he had in Ukraine. He lives with his wife and daughter in a dormitory with a shared kitchen on the floor. The family prefers to eat at the community centre canteen because of the insufficient social support and the difficulties of cooking in the common kitchen in the dormitory (RL5_RC2_C2_AT02)

The socio-economic support from organizations like Caritas played a critical role in providing financial aid and housing, helping her cope with the challenges of resettlement. However, the high cost of living and access to affordable food were notable hindrances (RL5_RC2_C2_AT05)

For P&C interviewees, two situations were reported:

Several factors are limiting a better food availability [in PAAL, Lisbon]: environmental conditions (water shortages), infrastructures (e.g., not adapted for better use of water) and policies: lack of more and better policy initiatives in the areas of environment, science and spatial / local planning, to enable more local production (RL5_RC2_C2_PT01)

These factors are essentially relevant as hindering changes [in PAAL, Lisbon]: physical and environmental conditions (poor terrain and water shortages), infrastructure (unsafe and poorly adapted to the good use of water) and economic and social conditions (poverty and weak interpersonal connections) were more evident. It was also noted the gap between the period of relocation / rehousing and the period of access to the garden, which blocked for seven years the possibility of healthy behaviours depending on better locally-based food [the woman had vegetable garden/yard next to the shack that was demolished and no one after, close to the apartment, for years] (RL5_RC2_C2_PT08).

Lastly, we considered the variable 'change in food waste practices' – for which we only obtained a total of twelve responses from Austria (4), Greece (2) and Portugal (6) – and used the same type of analysis (Table 18).

Table 18 – Level of connection between the enabling and hindering factors of behavioural change and the variable “Food waste practices has changed since the start of the Initiative”

Individual Resources	Enabling Factors of Change			Hindering Factors of Change		
	Austria	Greece	Portugal	Austria	Greece	Portugal
Time	0,8	0,3	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Money	0,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,3	0,0
Knowledge	0,6	0,7	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Education	0,2	0,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0
Perceived self-efficacy	0,2	0,2	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Access to equipment	0,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,2	0,0
Access to political and social actors	0,8	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Social Dynamics						
Being part community or social network	1,0	0,0	1,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Having significant relationships	1,0	0,8	1,0	0,0	0,2	0,0
Having certain beliefs and values	0,8	0,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Feelings of social appreciation	1,0	0,0	1,0	0,0	0,2	0,0
Structural Conditions						
Physical geography & environment	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,4	0,0	0,0
Infrastructure	0,0	0,0	1,0	0,2	0,7	0,0
Social and economic conditions	0,0	0,0	1,0	0,4	0,2	0,0
Policies and politics	0,2	0,0	0,0	0,6	0,7	0,0
Events and developments	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0

Table values between 0 and 1 – ratio between the number of ‘Yes’ answers (associations between the variable and each factor) of each country and the expected theoretical maximum (number of possible answers, matching each factor and each variable).

The enabling factors associated with changing practices in this domain show some similarities with the factors more closely linked to the other variables (those in Tables 15, 16 and 17). However, the addition of the ‘time’ factor seems to be significant among the individual resources:

Some time availability allows the interviewee to save money and thus reduce waste to a minimum (recycling and composting). This is the result of knowledge, associated with previous agricultural practices and previous employment, as well as perceived self-efficacy. This is transferred to some capacity to support neighbours. All these are factors that enable the change of behaviours (RL5_RC2_C1_PT01).

Plenty of time available, together with some economic relief, allows the interviewee to pay attention to details of convenient innovation, in the garden and at home, which are associated with relevant changes in behaviour in terms of food. This includes avoiding the waste by recycling with the composter (RL5_RC2_C2_PT02).

This reality, illustrated with examples from two different gardens in Portugal, allows us to interpret that greater availability of time, which is associated with other factors in changing behaviours and practices, corresponds to availability for actions that go beyond the most basic food production and usage activities, as was noticeable during the visits to the gardens.

With regard to social dynamics, ‘having relevant relationships’ is highlighted, as with other variables in previous analyses. Two examples that were reported are suggestive:

The fact that she had specific knowledge of food waste when cooking due to her participation in other NGOs, was an enabling factor (RL5_RC2_C1_GR02)

Being part of the community and having feelings of social appreciation are the factors of social dynamics that enable relevant behavioural changes in terms of food, but also the mitigation of the waste problem. These are factors that derive from the relationship with neighbours of different origins, in the community garden (RL5_RC2_C1_PT07)

In terms of structural factors, from those hindering the change in food waste practices, ‘politics and policies’ emerged with some relevance for the cases of Austria and Greece, but not for Portugal. In the latter case, the fact that two enabling factors were declared (‘infrastructure’ and ‘economic and

social conditions') due to local policies that facilitate the provision of composting equipment, as was seen on the ground in the case of Cascais, contributed to the lack of reference to hindering policies.

3.3.2. Change and gender+ inequalities within and across countries

The manifestation of change concerning gender+ inequality varies significantly across the cases analysed, largely due to the distinct nature of each initiative. In Austria and Turkey, the initiatives are focused on women's empowerment – directly so in Turkey, and indirectly within the framework of refugee support (especially for Ukrainians) in Austria.

As shown in Table 12, the indicator "Greater participation of women in the process of improving Food Security" yielded exclusively positive responses (Yes) in Austria and Turkey, with strong support from initiative members. In Greece, responses were negative, while in Portugal only half of respondents confirmed this. In Sweden, while there were no direct responses, one case provided a positive indication.

When illustrating these situations (including Greece), it is evident that not all cases are fully supportive of inclusive change processes:

"A key person in the central management of NG is a woman (37 years old)" and "The volunteers are mainly older women (pensioners)" (C2_RL5_SE02_CSO_1)

While the organiser of the initiative who is most at the centre of keeping activities going is a man in his thirties, the rest of the initiative largely builds on the engagement of women. The management consists mostly of women, and the volunteers who come to cook – especially the ones coming regularly – tend to be disproportionately more women than men (C2_RL5_SE01_CSO_1).

"Many of the volunteers of Boroume, who go to the markets to help facilitate the food-saving procedure, are women or people of other nationalities (...)" (C2_RL5_GR02_P)

"We regularly donate the vegetables from the garden that we have inside the prison of Tires, which is a garden managed by us, made by inmate women, but in which we have two colleagues there (...). Last year we had a production of 13 tons of fresh products: lettuces, onions, tomatoes... donated to charities... of social action". (C2_RL5_PT01_P_1)

"(...) [African immigrants] they are people who work a lot, and (...) normally have two jobs, mainly women: low wages; the men... it's the classic: they normally work on construction sites and the end of their afternoon is just drinking beer in the cafe. Women normally have two jobs: they go from one to the other, and therefore have very little time." (C2_RL5_PT01_P_1)

"All the people who have a vegetable garden here in the neighbourhood are of African origin (...). There are people who don't know how to read (...), interpret information from a leaflet that their children bring from school, sometimes really good things (...). The Cascais Authority, thus has (...) a giant number of responses to what are the ecological needs of the neighbourhood and, if we ask now that we need action in response to the need, we get some resources that effectively support us to give this response. But people (...), as a woman (...), I am of Cape Verdean origin (...) and my grandfather was a very proactive man, so he did a lot. I always saw him in the garden and doing a lot of things, but it was my grandmother who was always by his side giving directions (...); my mother has always been the person who goes to the garden (...)" (C2_RL5_PT01_CSO_1)

"The initiative seeks to empower women in the neighbourhood. It's not just about women coming to the garden to do some gardening work. The team's collective experiences in social services and the crucial actions they have undertaken together create a meaningful

impact. The team designs authentic empowering programmes for the neighbourhood women who participate in the garden. The garden functions primarily as a means for the team to facilitate empowerment opportunities for these women (...). The project's success highlights the community's active involvement. In the community garden, the women gardeners, during the summer, plant tomatoes, peppers, eggplants, okra, cucumbers and zucchini, while in winter, they grow Brussels sprouts, black cabbage, broccoli, green beans and broad beans twice a year (...). Since May 2021, the garden plots in Kadifekale have provided for women with a space to grow food for themselves and their families (...). In parallel, these workshops foster significant personal development and empowerment among women gardeners. The women openly express that they feel empowered, stronger, happier and more hopeful about their future. This personal transformation is truly inspiring and serves as a motivation for others to join the initiative. The local government plays a crucial role in supporting and facilitating the initiative, providing resources and assistance where needed. Moreover, the gardens also serve as a unifying force at the local government level, bolstering food security and citizen empowerment for the most vulnerable. Individually, the workshops and women-only circles provide spaces for building new alliances in personal and cultural struggles, fostering long-term relationships with the local authority based on trust, support, and compassion". (C2_RL5_TR01_P)

Users of the community garden call themselves "community garden women", as "being a community garden woman means getting stronger and empowered. A woman can do everything." (RL5_RC2_C1_TR01)

Refugees and locals benefit from increased social interaction, integration opportunities, and access to fresh, locally sourced food. Given the cooking opportunity, which is heavily oversubscribed, this adds to food access as in the asylum compartment private cooking is not allowed (for understandable reasons). Preparing the "own" food with cooking on the spot, and often based on self-produced vegetables is affecting the participants positively, also helps to keep own traditional alive. On Tuesdays a special women's day is organised to encourage women's participation, to empower women with regards participation and ownership in the garden but also to form a community beside the networks around the host camps of participants. There have been no noted negative impacts. (C2_RL5_AT01_CSO_1)

The management board includes several women involved in various organizational and operational roles. For example, one woman (...) leads an educational project for adults who lack formal education. Other roles include overseeing finances, managing organizational tasks, and coordinating activities such as sports programmes (...). The team is composed of about ten core members, with a significant number of women contributing to the leadership and direction of the initiative (...). The volunteer team includes a significant number of women and individuals with refugee backgrounds, there is one Ukrainian in staff (...). Additionally, the organization is working to increase the number of team members with a migration background, aiming for a more inclusive and representative team structure. While the current organization team comprises mostly of Austrian women, there is a conscious effort to involve more migrants and refugees in decision-making roles to reflect the diversity of the community they serve (C2_RL5_AT01_CSO_1)

The initiative has also fostered improved nutritional quality of diets, enhanced social inclusion, reduced inequalities, and a strengthened solidarity across social groups and classes, with a notable increase in the participation of women in food security efforts (C2_RL5_AT02_CSO_1)

In two cases, the initiatives highlight the crucial role of women – young women in Greece and older women in Sweden – in sustaining assistance programmes through voluntary work, supporting their goals without adopting a paternalistic welfare approach. In Portugal, one initiative involves incarcerated women in food production for social purposes, providing them with training and support from initiative members, which helps address gender disparities through skill-building. However, in another Portuguese case, certain immigrant women face additional labour demands related to food production and preparation. While this added responsibility can give women a degree of agency, it also leads to overwork, particularly among African-origin immigrant women, intensifying gender inequalities. This overburden hinders training opportunities, empowerment and gradual change, though small shifts do occasionally occur.

These situations underscore the need for policy measures and collaborative governance that foster learning, empowerment and resilience while also being attentive to the existing workload shouldered by women, as discussed in the following sections.

In another case (Turkey), the municipality allocates both human and material resources to empower women while fostering social learning that particularly benefits children and young people, with positive impacts on agri-food practices and health. This municipal effort is strengthened by complementary partnerships, including both internal ones with specialised municipal departments and external ones with civil society organizations.

According to many women involved, empowerment is the most significant outcome, as their engagement in gardening directly supports food security, quality of life and health. However, the initiative's potential is limited by a shortage of land, preventing more women from participating and restricting usage to just one year per user.

In Austria, women's involvement is prominent in supporting the reception and integration of refugees on three levels: within the initiative's leadership, among volunteers (including individuals with immigrant backgrounds), and among the refugee population itself. The focus on food security, supported by education and training, positions many women as key agents of behavioural change, fostering empowerment and integration for vulnerable individuals and promoting resilience throughout the community.

Discussions and Conclusions

4. Overall Discussion and Recommendations

Across the ten case studies, a core objective was to understand how initiatives targeting food security catalysed behavioural changes in terms of access to food, healthy diets and combating waste, at individual and community levels. These goals were primarily pursued through community gardens that supported local food production and diversified food sources, along with food distribution networks that included food waste mitigation. Key findings readjust some of the results achieved with earlier research (RC1). While financial constraints continue to emerge as a major barrier at the micro-level, affecting both individuals and stakeholders, knowledge, education and perceived self-efficacy act as key enablers at that level. Social conditions (e.g. having relevant relationships or being part of a community) generally support change, while structural conditions (macro-level factors) mainly stimulate or challenge stakeholders. Consequently, most enablers are situated at micro- and meso levels. Participation in the initiatives was the primary catalyst for change, fostering collaboration, engagement and capacity building for marginalised groups. The participation provides training, resources and opportunities for involvement in food production and community activities, thus enhancing empowerment and social integration, especially for women and refugees. Structural factors, in turn (in particular economic and social conditions, the environment and politics and policies), often constrain vulnerable populations. Yet, they also enable broader changes at the stakeholder level.

Throughout this work, various factors were identified that influence individual and collective behavioural changes in response to food security challenges and sustainable food practices. In terms of collective behaviour, we observed the activities of organisations leading the ten analysed initiatives. Each case had unique circumstances, with organisations adapting their support to fit the diverse vulnerabilities of their target populations. Behavioural shifts and related social practices – ranging from local food production and consumption patterns to waste reduction – are shaped by these organisational and social characteristics, especially in the context of a gender-equitable, socially just environmental transition.

In Austria, for example, organisations predominantly focus on receiving and integrating immigrants, especially Ukrainian refugees. Here, key enablers include education, knowledge, self-efficacy, and access to resources and support from political and social actors. Financial limitations, however, were a common barrier across cases. Volunteering, particularly in Austria and Sweden (with less reference in Greece and Portugal), contributed time as an enabler of change.

In Greece, initiatives are centred around solidarity, social integration and combating food insecurity and waste. Interviewees, predominantly with secondary education, highlighted knowledge (specifically in healthy food preparation, environmental awareness and circular practices) as the primary driver of change.

Swedish initiatives, led by social assistance organisations, aim to provide healthy food to highly marginalised groups in an environmentally sustainable manner. Similar to Greece, but with a stronger welfare focus, these efforts emphasise the enabling role of factors like volunteer time and donations, food and equipment access, and, crucially, food literacy and related skills.

Portuguese initiatives focus on urban and community gardens as tools for promoting food security, healthy diets and waste reduction, with the broader objective of societal transformation. Interviewees

– diverse in their vulnerability levels – identified time as an ambivalent factor. While it allowed for gradual improvements in garden resources, it hindered overworked individuals, especially African-origin women, who are often involved in other community roles. Knowledge and self-efficacy were additional key enablers, helping to mitigate economic and educational gaps.

In Turkey, similar to Portugal, vegetable gardens serve as a means of resilience within a socio-political context supported by grassroots movements impacting the agri-food sector. Although some previous initiatives struggled, these Turkish cases illustrate perseverance and resilience, highlighting the importance of consistent support in the face of unmet promises by the state to address food security and extreme poverty. Then mayor Tunç Soyer's "Neighbourhood Gardens" initiative in Izmir, based on the vision of "Alternative Agriculture is Possible" and "Equal Citizenship," exemplifies this impact by creating inclusive spaces that empower individuals, especially vulnerable groups, to take control of their food sources and narratives.

Across these initiatives, several factors enable changes in both individual and collective behaviours. In all countries, being part of a community or social network and establishing meaningful relationships were significant enablers, followed closely by a sense of social appreciation, particularly in Austria. Additionally, certain beliefs and values, especially among immigrant populations, positively influenced behaviours but occasionally acted as barriers (marginal references in cases from Austria and Portugal). But it should be noted that, in all the cases observed, the referred enabling factors are tied to integration contexts, where language and communication skills between the actors in the changes are crucial, and reflect the differentiated social capital – bonding, bridging and linking – that individuals and collectives can develop in supportive socio-political environments.

Structural conditions (macro-level factors) also played a role, shaped by the unique characteristics of each initiative. Positive and negative structural conditions often held similar weights. In Greece and Sweden, unfavourable factors (e.g., climate, international conflicts exacerbating poverty, lack of public support, and costly transport) hindered change without counterbalancing enablers. Conversely, Austria's cases underscored enabling conditions like economic and social support, favourable politics and policies, and social inclusion initiatives supporting refugee integration. In Turkey, municipal policies were a significant enabler amidst worsening economic, social and political conditions and severe issues in infrastructure including water scarcity and energy-based pollution. In Portugal, structural conditions such as water and soil limitations posed substantial constraints, though local policies and events offered some relief.

Four main categories of outcomes emerged from the initiatives, as detailed in Table 19:

- (1) Increased access to food production spaces and improved practices of enhancing self-sufficiency and promoting healthy diets.
- (2) increased environmental awareness through composting, waste reduction and organic practices.
- (3) enhanced food security and nutrition, including improved diets and waste reduction.
- (4) greater social integration and empowerment, especially for women and marginalised groups.

Table 19 –Key outcomes of initiatives driving behavioural change

		Austria (AT)		Greece (GR)		Portugal (PT)		Sweden (SE)		Turkey (TR)	
Main outcomes of initiatives ↓	Initiatives / cases →	01	02	01	02	01	02	01	02	01	02
• Increased local food production (AT) • access to soil / to garden space / to gardening (GR, PT,TR) • access to produce from the garden (GR) • better practices of food / organic production (PT,TR) • more diverse, more continuous and healthier vegetable production (PT)		X		X		X	X			X	X
• Knowledge on environmental practices as composting, organic production (AT, PT) • raising awareness and (environmental) education about food, healthy diet, climate change, soil, sustainability (ecological vegetable production) (PT, TR) • Reduced food waste in the city (SE)		X				X	X		X	X	X
• Improved food security and nutrition (AT,TR) • access to warm, healthy, nutritious, plant-based meals (GR,SE) • better cooking (meal preparation), choice and practice (AT) • exposure to food that would be wasted (GR) • improved diet (greater integration of vegetables) and with better quality (PT)		X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
• Resilient community networks, access to a social network and /or social integration (AT,SE,TR) • well-being, feeling of care and sense of belonging (AT,GR,SE) • access to hygiene + volunteering opportunity for non-Swedish speakers (SE) • enhanced self-efficacy, also gender specific (AT) / self-sufficiency and increased self-love and value: women's empowerment (TR) • resource sharing (including food) in the garden (PT) • increased physical, mental, social, environmental well-being (PT,TR) • safe and community spaces of encounter for women + reclaiming a space of mental restoration (garden) after trauma (house dislocation) (TR)		X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X

These outcomes highlight shifts in local food production, environmental practices and social solidarity, addressing multi-dimensional goals of sustainable food security.

The following sections analyse pathways for transformation inspired by these outcomes and discuss necessary policies to support these shifts. Recognised research limitations and suggestions for future research will also be outlined, followed by public policy recommendations to further promote these positive changes.

4.1. Paths and links to transformation

In organizing the information gathered to explore ways to transform food systems in favour of vulnerable populations from a gender+ perspective, and considering the behaviours required to achieve these changes, the use of "better stories" may serve as a valuable tool due to their illustrative and suggestive potential. However, given the diversity and intrinsic complexity of the cases studied, a comparative synthesis of factors and processes across cases (Table 20) may better reveal the enabling conditions for change. These factors fall into three categories:

- **Collaborative networks and partnerships:** involving civil society organizations, municipalities and volunteer networks, fostering resource sharing and knowledge exchange.
- **Leadership and organizational framework:** proactive municipal involvement, strong organisational support and committed leadership were pivotal in driving change.

- **Cultural and contextual sensitivity:** initiatives tailored to community needs with adaptive approaches, incorporating education, training and trust-building.

Table 20 – Key factors influencing outcomes

		Austria (AT)		Greece (GR)		Portugal (PT)		Sweden (SE)		Turkey (TR)		
Determinants of the outcomes ↓	Initiatives / cases →	01	02	01	02	01	02	01	02	01	02	
• Outreach to other volunteer social organisations & wider community (AT) • Many collaborations with organisations ranging from supermarkets to boot camps + collaborations of many charitable institutions creating a very large network (GR) • The role of suitable partnerships (PT) • A network of proactive engaged volunteers (GR,SE) • Embeddedness in a large network of similar organisations and food producers/ wholesalers (SE) • Continuous and trusting communication on / through various social media (GR,SE) • Partnership with civil society organisations who have expertise in women's issues (TR)		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
• Proactive municipality / active, highly committed organisers / proactive leadership of managing association (AT,PT,SE) • financial support: crowdfunding and municipality (SE) • women representation in direction boards and decision making (GR) • Local Administration/the Mayor: strong commitment to achieving equal citizenship and genuine interest in vulnerable populations and ecological values and sustainable agri-food systems (TR) • supportive community + continuous participation (and mobility cost coverage) + visibility (AT) • municipal policy following Environmental Education principles and transforming mere "Urban Gardens" into "Community Gardens" (PT) • active social service employees on the ground, developing one-to-one communication and bond with the participants based on trust (TR)		X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
• Cultural adaptation / sensitive approach and accessibility of services + complex offers / a bundle of activities hosted in the Community Centre + close integration with sustainable food processing like those processing excess food as social projects (AT) • patient and engaged employees and regularly coming volunteers + love and care put into the state and look of the venue + trained (and confident) cooks who know how to make food (SE) • inclusive, supportive, and caring environment in the garden (TR) • influence of other users of the garden, including mutual assistance (PT) • organizing a series of workshops (GR) • workshops run based on the needs of the women participants by the municipality team on the ground • implementation of educational programmes at schools (GR)		X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X

The conditions for replicating these successful transformations are summarised in table 21, organised into three primary categories of influencing factors.

Table 21 – Determinants of replicability: success factors for driving behavioural change

		Austria (AT)		Greece (GR)		Portugal (PT)		Sweden (SE)		Turkey (TR)		
Replicability determinants ↓	Initiatives / cases →	01	02	01	02	01	02	01	02	01	02	
• Local partnerships + acceptance of innovative solutions beyond the traditional social support organisations + outreach to group through facilitators network (AT) • strategic partnerships involving services for local social innovation (PT) • commitment to establishing trust-based long standing relationships with communities with a participatory approach (TR) • Connections with local producers and their fields where products are cultivated and produce is taken + a strong social network of contributors (GR) • engaged social network of volunteers and contributors (SE)		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
• Strong organisational framework as organising place & cost coverage to commute + active gardener and steering group + scalability of the scarce funding sources also vis-a-vis other support organisations for people in		X	X	X		X		X	X	X	X	

need (AT) • proactivity of the municipal company (PT,TR) • requests for support from other municipalities (PT) • financial and material support to guarantee regular food provision + provision of food from numerous food stores and wholesalers + access to a locality where to cook in a safe way and at large scale (SE) • provision of material and immaterial resources (PT,TR) • Organised garden in which people from vulnerable groups have access to cultivate, access produce, and also learn about the production of food (GR)										
• Culturally sensitive approach (AT, TR) free of bias, prejudices, and racism (TR) • group specific knowledge to ensure response to needs + flexible, needs based changes (AT) • Multilingualism for better intercultural communication and understanding in diverse communities (TR)	X	X							X	X

In this table, the first category highlights the mobilization of social capital through partnerships, a foundation often linked to social innovation. The second category includes behaviours that extend this foundation, integrating current realities with aspirational goals for transformational change. This often requires additional resources to address identified gaps or inadequacies. The third category focuses on cultural sensitivity, effective communication and adaptive flexibility, all crucial in navigating evolving contexts and supporting holistic approaches. Ultimately, the replicability of these successful transformations relies on robust social networks, proactive municipal policies and culturally inclusive approaches that are responsive to specific socio-political contexts.

4.2. Policy crossovers

Food security is at the forefront of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the 2030 Agenda, aligning directly with SDG 2 (Zero Hunger) and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production). At the European level, this aligns with the Farm to Fork (F2F) strategy, which prioritises decarbonizing food systems and promoting sustainable, equitable, and fair food production practices. Our focus on sustainable food security, encompassing a comprehensive, inclusive and gender-sensitive approach, highlights the interconnections with other SDGs that shape a broad range of public policies. Beyond SDG 2 and SDG 12, these include, but are not limited to, SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being), SDG 4 (Quality Education), SDG 5 (Gender Equality), SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), and SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals). Each of these goals contributes to an integrated framework, which we explore further below.

Building on the determinants for replicability identified in Table 21 (success factors influencing behavioural change) and insights from interviews with various stakeholders, we propose a coherent set of policy areas essential for enabling sustainable food security. This vision aligns with "regenerative sustainability," a concept that has emerged as central to the dialogues surrounding the UN Food Systems Summits (2021, 2024). Therefore, integrated social, economic and environmental policies, guided by effective governance processes, are crucial to achieving sustainable outcomes.

The first category in Table 21, which highlights the mobilization of relational and social capital within organisations – often reflective of social innovation – corresponds to broad-reaching policies, such as those outlined in the ACCTING Research Lines. These policies should intersect to foster community-led processes that build resilience and food security by empowering vulnerable groups, particularly women. This entails acknowledging the importance of localised food networks and supply chains facilitated by public entities, regional or local authorities, and NGOs that can drive partnerships and networks. These alliances reinforce shared responsibility under national policies framed within European or broader international contexts.

The second and third categories underscore the unique contributions of our research, derived from case studies with perspectives not captured by previous research. By examining case studies from Northern, Central and Southern / Mediterranean Europe with diverse vulnerability profiles, including gender+ considerations, our findings highlight factors of behavioural change – especially the interplay between individual and collective/organizational shifts – that add nuances and depth to established knowledge. Amidst current global and European environmental, political and geopolitical challenges that pose both threats and opportunities for food security, the identified policy areas must operate interactively and align with strategies and programmes promoting a sustainable food transition, which, in turn, supports broader sustainability transitions across scales.

Recognizing this context, and acknowledging that the replicability of successful initiatives demands reimagined economic provisions within the scope of a plural economy⁴, we identify the following intersecting policy areas focused on food security, health (personal and environmental), and the inclusive, emancipatory participation of vulnerable groups from a gender+ perspective:

- **Integration of social and sectoral policies:** this includes cohesive policies spanning the economy, health, agriculture, environment and social inclusion, covering areas such as immigrant reception and integration, gender equality, and social cohesion.
- **Research and science policies:** emphasizing cross-disciplinary research, these policies should connect social sciences, humanities, natural sciences, and legal, political and civic studies. The goal is to translate findings into action-research initiatives, participatory planning, and “in-context” training for vulnerable groups.
- **Development, planning, and territorial cohesion policies:** these policies prioritise resource allocation at the local level, tailored to meet proximity planning needs and support the inclusion of vulnerable populations, particularly in terms of food security and health.
- **Policies for expanding strategic partnerships and networking:** aimed at extending the reach of partnerships within and beyond multilevel governance, these policies should align with the subsidiarity principle, adjusting European and national political agendas to optimise the impact of local resource allocation.

These policy areas must also address foundational aspects of governance and democratic processes, as implied by a pertinent question from Turkish researchers:

“(…) The urgent need for more initiatives that specifically target vulnerable groups is a significant gap in our current food security landscape. Possible question: How can it be possible to understand that protecting the right to healthy food for vulnerable groups is not just an individual issue but a collective social struggle?”.

This reflective synthesis provides a basis for outlining key directions for policy recommendations, as detailed below.

4.3. Research gaps and directions for future research

The strength of this research design lies in its comparative analysis, which spans diverse socio-political contexts and provides a nuanced understanding of how intersectional gender+ inequalities interlinks with food security and sustainable food systems. Nonetheless, there are certain limitations and gaps that future research could address.

⁴ Plural economy as comprising different dimensions: market, non-market, public, domestic/family, social, solidarity, relational, cooperative, urban, local, regional, rural, territorial, agricultural, industrial, fishing, tourism, distribution, cultural, institutional, network, microeconomics, macroeconomics, green, blue, circular, environmental, etc.

One limitation involves case selection. Focusing predominantly on urban and peri-urban areas may limit the extrapolation of findings to rural settings. Expanding the research to include rural food systems could provide a more comprehensive view of the challenges faced by women across different socio-geographical contexts.

Including additional case studies across both urban, peri-urban, and rural areas could further diversify the range of initiatives, capturing perspectives from varied actors – public, private, or a combination thereof. This diversity would allow for a richer understanding of food resource management approaches and behavioural shifts towards sustainable and regenerative diets and lifestyles. Such expanded perspectives could encompass critical analyses of resilience and resistance among people facing gender+ inequalities and other vulnerabilities, spanning domestic, community and more complex domains involving power dynamics, multiple stakeholders and territorial considerations.

Another limitation stems from the reliance on qualitative interviews. While qualitative data offer detailed insights, they do not capture systemic patterns or provide quantifiable measures of the initiatives' impact. Integrating quantitative data on the long-term effects of these initiatives on food security and gender equality could significantly enhance the research.

Furthermore, additional research is needed on the adaptability of these initiatives in response to changing economic, environmental or political conditions. Scenario-building exercises that anticipate change and incorporate citizen and stakeholder participation could help address this gap. Additionally, quantitative measurements of the alignment and effectiveness of these initiatives with broader policies at various levels could foster a more consistent and intertwined approach to gender+ inclusion within sustainability efforts.

An emerging area for future research is the role of digital tools and technologies in advancing sustainable food systems and gender inclusion. With the growth of digital agriculture and e-governance, examining how technology can empower – or, conversely, present obstacles for – marginalised groups within food systems is essential for understanding the evolving landscape of food security and inclusivity.

4.4. Directions for policy recommendations

Achieving food security and sustainability extends beyond environmental considerations; it includes a critical social dimension, ensuring equitable access to healthy, sustainable food, community cohesion and the empowerment of marginalised populations. In alignment with the European Green Deal's ambitious environmental and climate goals, there is a need to strengthen gender-sensitive frameworks within its implementation. This would ensure that social dimensions, including intersectional vulnerabilities, are addressed explicitly.

Our analysis of various initiatives demonstrates their effectiveness in enhancing local food production, food security, environmental stewardship, social inclusion, and gender empowerment, particularly among refugee and low-income populations. These initiatives have also fostered behavioural change by addressing motivation, capability and opportunities for communities to adopt secure and sustainable food practices.

Based on these insights, we recommend that policies target specific actions addressing multilevel barriers (from micro to meso levels, focusing on individual, community and social capital) that often restrict vulnerable populations – particularly women – from fully participating in sustainable food initiatives. These barriers are typically related to gender norms, financial constraints and a limited access to decision-making roles. To strengthen these recommendations, and as a continuation of previously discussed cross-sectoral policy priorities, it is crucial to:

1. **Encourage cross-sectoral policy integration**

Develop policies that link food security with health, education and environmental issues to maximise impact. For example, public health policies should consider the territorial aspects of food systems, and agricultural practices should be integrated into land-use planning and management. These areas offer opportunities for necessary public participation and collaborative governance.

2. **Adapt policies to local contexts**

Ensure flexibility in policy implementation to account for Europe's diverse territorial contexts, while maintaining core policy principles. This means to assume differences in action required for areas with different levels of active involvement of citizens and structuring of local governance. An example inspired by our study would be the possible adjustment of programmes focused on urban gardens so that women's empowerment by means of urban agriculture could be enhanced and extended to women who work outside their neighbourhoods and for long hours.

3. **Strengthen partnerships across sectors**

Promote collaboration between local governments, civil society, academia and the private sector to build resilient networks that support and empower vulnerable communities in their struggle to achieve better food security, sustainable consumption and food waste mitigation. Such partnerships can leverage a broad range of resources and expertise to drive sustainable change.

4. **Support local strategic food resource planning**

Encourage strategic and participatory planning at the local level for spaces that facilitate access to local food resources, such as community gardens and reception centres. These spaces can connect extra-market food distribution agents with citizens in need, with solidarity organizations acting as intermediaries and supported by appropriate political-administrative authorities.

5. **Expand sustainable urban and peri-urban agriculture for vulnerable groups**

Promote the sustainable expansion of urban or peri-urban agricultural areas for vulnerable groups, with the option for extended or rotational land use beyond a single season. Such initiatives should operate under participatory planning and monitoring processes to allow for dynamic and responsible readjustments.

These recommendations advocate for an inclusive approach to food security policies that harness the strengths of cross-sectoral collaboration, local adaptability and empowerment of vulnerable groups, ensuring that food security and sustainability contribute to broader societal goals of equity, resilience and community well-being.

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